

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D2.1: KPIs, implementation plan and demo implementation of SRI

WP2 – Business cases and their demonstrations

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Executive Summary

This deliverable introduces into the 7 heterogeneous business cases and demonstrations of BlueBird and their plans for implementing the project and evaluating project achievements on demonstration level.

It defines the general functionality of the BlueBird system via the presentation of the high-level use case system that contains functionalities (e.g., optimization, market integration) and affected assets (e.g., EV charging stations, heat pumps), so that these can be merged into specific use cases at the pilots' sites.

Then it presents the BlueBird evaluation system consisting of KPIs in three different domains and approaches to KPI calculation, both for process and for impact related KPIs (which includes SRI monitoring), focusing on the impact of BlueBird.

Finally, it presents detailed descriptions of the starting positions at the pilot sites, of their technical and social fabric, the specific use cases they intend to apply and the implementation plans through which pilot partners intend to realize the use cases.

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Acronyms and Definitions

Table 1: Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
AC	Air Conditioning
API	Application Programming Interface
AMB	Area Metropolitana de Barcelona
BE	Barcelona Energia
BMS	Building Management System
CCB	Centre Civic Building
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CS	Cold Storage
CTM	Centralized Technical Management
DoA	Description of the Action
DR	Demand Response
DSM	Demand-side Management
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DSR	Demand-side Response
DT	Digital Twin
EC	(Centralized) Energy Center
EMS	Energy Management System
EV	Electrical Vehicle
G2V	Grid to Vehicle
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GUI	Graphic User Interface
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
HV/MV/LV	High Voltage/Medium Voltage/Low Voltage
IEB	Illa Esportiva Building
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MB	Montcada Building
MPC	Model Predictive Control
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
PLB	Prinz Luitpold Bad Hotel
PSNC	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center
PV	Photovoltaic
REN	Renewable Energy Network
SCOP	Seasonal Coefficient of Performance

SC	Space Cooling
SH	Space Heating
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TM	Trading Manager
TSO	Transmission System Operator
T&T	Tour & Taxis site
UC	Use Case
VIG	Vehicle to Grid
VPP	Virtual Power Plant
WP	Work Package

I. INTRODUCTION

WP 2 provides the groundwork of the BlueBird system of functionalities and interaction both inside the software system and externally (e.g., regarding business case or regulation analysis). This is where the local conditions are analysed and handed over to the technical teams to generate system components that are then implemented at the demo sites to provide feedback to the technical teams and convey to understand if their requirements have been met. All this is done in an agile process that contains the following elements:

- *Documentation* of the actual situation, challenges, objectives and plans of the demo partners, identification of stakeholders and their constraints as well as documentation of technical and social infrastructure and regulation issues.
- Common creation of *use cases (UC)* where all related project participants gathered in a cumulative knowledge building process to develop high level use cases and determine necessary functional building blocks, also in terms of the “BlueBird services” that essentially are sub-use cases of the high-level use cases.
- Demo partners’ *implementation plans* presenting how they envision the execution of the use cases in their pilot case.
- Definition of *KPIs* that cover not only optimization criteria, but the general objectives of the project; the most prominent among these being the EU metric for buildings equipped with flexibility services, the Smart Building Readiness Indicator (SRI),¹ and the so-called BlueBird SRI that additionally covers the specific services created by the project to enhance flexibility of buildings’ energy demands as a prerequisite of buildings’ grid integration.

As the project is built around its demonstrations, the demo descriptions should integrate the UCs and the according implementation plans. Therefore, the deliverable is structured as follows:

1. The first chapter deals with the BlueBird UC system, explaining the functional building blocks and their organization.
2. The second chapter presents the BlueBird evaluation framework, focusing on core KPIs, that all demo partners need to monitor, specific KPIs that they need to track for their specific UCs and situations and evaluation methods available.
3. The third chapter, finally, presents the demo descriptions and UCs created in the first 6 months of the project (including technical & social infrastructure, regulation, etc.), the implementation plans set up at the end of this period and the specific KPIs that each demo will monitor.

¹ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator_en

II. THE BLUEBIRD USE CASE SYSTEM

II.1. Methodology

The EU project BlueBird will deliver a toolset to unlock building energy flexibility, targeting both social and technical flexibility and combining them into a set of flexibility services that can be combined in a modular way to foster replicability.

This toolset is made up by Use Cases (UCs), that are based on the original definition in the DoA. These were, however, amended and refined through discussions not only among the demo partners, but also with the socio-technical work packages WP3-WP7. This discussion also covered practical issues, e.g., the availability of data, consent and agreement from affected stakeholders. A formal UC template was used to document the results of the discussion and is serving as communication means between the software coding team, the demos and technical teams. These UC descriptions (in XLS files) are available as separate additions to this deliverable.

Essentially, the UCs are unique for each demo case and they are expected to end up with software and recommendation system that can be replicated by external building owners or managers. Therefore, at the end of the UC discussion process mentioned above, the original use cases were slightly adapted, rewritten, amended and names changed to enable the creation of a consistent, modular BlueBird use case system. This system, developed with the participation of almost all project partners and work packages, will be presented and shortly explained in the next section.

For each demo partner, this use case system is instantiated, and also presented graphically in the demo descriptions' sections.

II.2. Use Case System

The BlueBird use case system is organized along two axes:

- The energy sector, i.e., *heat*, provided by heat pumps, gas, a heat grid or geothermal sources or *electricity* for equipment or EV charging, amongst others.
- The functionality components to be provided by the BlueBird System. These functionalities are clustered into a set of high-level use cases that include services which can be chosen as components based on the specific situations at a pilot's partners site.

The specific UCs for the demo partners are then generated by combining these two axes, and of course adding specific circumstances and constraints. This method allows for dealing with UCs from a generic point of view, while at the same time allowing room for replication and the specifics of each demo partner.

As can be seen in Figure 1 the high-level use cases comprise a logical suite of functionalities, which will be explained step by step below:

The first step is a groundwork component that in general deals with forecasting the status of the assets and the energy demand in the future, which in the context of the BlueBird system is "the next time-step". To this end, predictions of external factors (e.g., weather, PV harvest) are integrated into digital twins (DTs) of different levels of asset aggregations (no aggregation, room, floor, etc) and calculate a new DT status.

Figure 1: UC logical suite

As a next main functionality, the input from the DT is then used to optimize the system, using the optimization criterion and constraints defined for the demo cases. Generally, the optimization can be done in an *integrated way*, i.e., optimizing across energy sectors, or within one energy sectors, i.e., from a *silo* perspective. The nature of the output of this optimization differs across pilots and across UCs; this is why the graphic differentiates:

- if the optimization is merely technical, i.e., implemented as model predictive control (MPC), i.g., an automation of the physical system,
- if it includes an “acknowledgement” functionality for e.g., technical managers, which means it is cancelled if the acknowledgement is not given in a specific time window (Ackn & MPC), or
- if it merely generates information that then can be turned into recommendations for behaviour change for the building inhabitants, with the understanding that the implementation of these suggestions is by far not certain (End-User Information).

The result of this optimization then has to be evaluated not only regarding the optimization objectives but also regarding other KPIs, as for instance the result on the level of PV self-consumption, although the optimization criterion might be purely economically motivated. Therefore, the impact assessment is the next functional component.

In case the optimization output is not an automation via MPC or an acknowledgement for an automation (Ackn & MPC), the information for user recommendations needs to be transformed into a specific form of user recommendation (e.g., “charge EV now”) and communicated to the end-users (i.g., staff or inhabitants). This may be implemented via a web-interface or an app, but also other communication options as for instance push-notifications via emails are possible. The main objective of this functionality is to create a high probability of inhabitants implementing the suggested behaviour change options (e.g., a flexible time window for EV charging).

The optimization compared to the baseline simulation of the DT brings to light the flexibility potential that can be valorised through different flexibility markets: creating bidding strategies for the explicit (i.e., regulation or capacity markets) flexibility markets. This functionality is covered by the “market interaction” high level use case, that includes the “physical” implementation of a market interaction, e.g., via a DSO interface, where needed. This is the final step in the UC functionality system.

Aside of this, the results of the optimization and impact analysis can also be used to provide a study-based understanding of potential extensions of a consumer basis for a given grid.

This generic UC system is then instantiated for each pilot and integrated in the demo descriptions. In these sections, the specific use cases are contextualized, reflecting the local conditions, and unique implementation settings of each pilot. To point this out visually, equipment and functionalities not used in a pilot are greyed out.

III. THE BLUEBIRD EVALUATION FRAMEWORK AND KPIs

The evaluation of complex energy efficiency and flexibility projects requires a comprehensive approach that captures both the activities undertaken and the actual changes these activities produce. This is why the BlueBird evaluation framework distinguishes between process evaluation and impact evaluation.

Process evaluation focuses on countable metrics that document project activities and deliverables. These are the tangible outputs that demonstrate the project has been executed according to plan, including metrics such as the number of workshops conducted, papers published, or number of buildings using the project system. While important for project management and accountability, process metrics alone cannot demonstrate whether the project has achieved its intended goals.

Impact evaluation, in contrast, addresses the fundamental question of whether the software packages and recommendations created and applied in the pilot implementations have generated the expected outcomes. This includes assessing whether the solutions have led to increased flexibility in energy systems, decreased energy consumption, improved empowerment of the inhabitants, and if they successfully avoided rebound effects where energy savings might be offset by increased consumption elsewhere.

This distinction is critical because a project can successfully complete all planned activities (strong process metrics) while failing to achieve meaningful impact through demonstrating real-world changes. In the end, demonstrating real-world changes is the ultimate measure of success. The framework presented here provides a structured approach to measuring these impacts across technical, economic, and social dimensions.

III.1. Design Aspects of the Impact Assessment Evaluation Framework

The BlueBird Evaluation Framework is built upon several key design considerations that ensure comprehensive and meaningful evaluation. These design aspects address fundamental questions about what, when, and how to measure project impacts.

- **Defining What to Measure: Concepts, Metrics, and KPIs**

First of all, concepts that represent project goals need to be determined, spanning the three primary domains: *technical* performance, *economic* viability, and *social* acceptance. For instance, what do we mean by asking for resilience? How do we define flexibility? What encompasses the empowerment of inhabitants? Once these concepts are clearly understood, they must be translated into metrics. Metrics answer the question, how a concept is measured. For instance, flexibility might be conceptualized as increasing or decreasing energy demand in terms of kW for a certain period of time upon request. They can then be measured in kWh over this certain period of time or in terms of offering a certain percentage of the peak energy consumption over a certain period of time (%).

KPIs, Key Performance indicators are the most important concepts that should be measured, but they also include a normative element defining in which direction an important metric should develop in order to be called a success. This could be to increase the percentage of peak energy provided or achieve a certain value of flexibility in terms of kW to be offered on a flexibility market.

The BlueBird framework further differentiates between so-called “core KPIs” that are measured consistently across all pilots and supplementary indicators, that are relevant only to specific implementations, addressing unique characteristics of individual demonstration sites and UCs.

- **Baseline versus Baseline-Free KPIs**

Whenever KPIs compare different situations, be it temporally or be it a comparison with other entities, it is necessary to have a baseline against which a former or a different situation can be compared. In some cases, the baseline is simply the value before an intervention which can be compared against the value after the intervention. But in many cases the construction of baselines entails a considerable effort, because it needs to compare a real situation, e.g. a power profile after

a flexibility action against a power profile without flexibility. This implies a simulation of the encountered system without the implemented flexibility action. Digital Twins (DTs) can help construct this baseline.

There is a huge body of literature about baseline construction. Being such a complex undertaking, the generation of baselines can be avoided by defining “baseline-free” KPIs, with normally absolute values. This could be, for instance, a certain value of kW flexibility needed for the participation in a specific market.

- **Establishing System Boundaries and Focus**

Clear system boundaries are essential for meaningful evaluation. For each metric and KPI, and individually for each pilot, the framework requires an explicit definition of whether measurements apply to entire buildings, specific energy subsystems, or particular components. This clarity ensures that results are interpretable and comparable across different contexts.

- **Determining Temporal and Intervention-Based Measurement**

The framework specifies both when measurements should occur and what triggers measurement activities. Time-based measurements are scheduled at specific project milestones, including baseline measurements before deployment, measurements after each deployment phase, and final assessments at project completion. Intervention-based KPI monitoring relates to the evaluation of specific interventions and experiments. This dual approach ensures comprehensive data collection while maintaining efficiency.

- **Selecting Measurement Methods**

The framework uses multiple measurement approaches depending on the nature of each KPI and the situations in the various pilots. In general, baseline KPIs are to be preferred against baseline-free KPIs; which is supported through DTs creation. Generally, the direct calculation of measurable effects is preferable to simulations and even to surveys, however in some pilots there will be a step-by-step approach to implementing direct control. This implies that in many cases simulations are at least part of the scheme in the first steps. Surveys are used to capture user perceptions and behaviors; however, as there are not sufficient inhabitants in some of the pilots, these need to be amended by qualitative interviews. As mentioned above, the temporal granularity is based on the situational context. For the core KPIs there will be at least one measurement before the deployment phase, one at the end of the project and at least one more after first deployments to understand if the project is on the right track. These measurements will be amended by intervention-based evaluations for partial deployments and experiments.

This methodological flexibility is a strong point of this framework as it combines robust, theoretic-grounded methods with practicability at pilot sites. Figure 2 shows this methodological toolset.

Figure 2: KPI structure

III.2. Social, Economic, and Technical Core KPIs for Impact Assessment

The BlueBird project organizes its impact evaluation around three interconnected concept domains, each addressing a critical dimension of building energy flexibility and performance.

Some of the KPIs are more complex than others, namely, flexibility and resilience. For these an expert discussion with experts within the project was organized based on a literature analysis.

For flexibility, the main issue was the huge variety of KPIs in literature. The group of BlueBird experts therefore selected a subset of KPIs researched in literature based on the main categories needed: absolute and relative flexibility, and the performance of flexibility activities, which are key for the reliability as of demand side flexibility as a contribution to grid resilience.

For resilience, the conceptual definition proved to be a challenge.

There is no general definition of building resilience. From the definition analysis of Castaño-Rosa 2022 one could start a definition with "Building resilience refers to the capacity of a building to withstand, timely and efficiently recover from and mitigate the impacts of external disturbances, such as climate threats, like extreme wind or heat, flooding, fire, or earthquakes."

In addition, "existing frameworks [for urban resilience] highlight preparedness, agility, participatory, restorative, adaptability, and robustness as key attributes for resilience" (Castaño-Rosa 2022). Therefore, a resilience of a building includes its ability to adapt and respond to changes while maintaining structure and functions. Functionality is rather vaguely described, such as in the following statements:

"A resilient building is a building that not only is robust but also can fulfil its functional requirements (withstand) during a major disruption. Its performance might even be disrupted but has to recover to an acceptable level in a timely manner in order to avoid disaster impacts." Maozami 2019.

"The functional requirements define what a building has to do, and the performance requirements determine how well a functional requirement has to be done." Wilde 2018.

According to Wilde 2018 *functional requirements* describe the essential purposes of a building including those to enable occupancy and use, such as to ensure structural safety, provide lighting, maintain a healthy indoor environmental quality including thermal comfort and indoor air quality. *Performance requirements* on the other hand, describe the measurable level at which those functions must be achieved: Indoor temperature between X–Y °C, Maximum structural deformation under load, CO₂ concentration below a threshold, or recovery time after disruption.

In short for the context of the project, we can assume the definition:

Building resilience refers to the capacity of a building to maintain functionality and provide comfort and essential services in the face of external disruptions, particularly those related to energy supply, grid instability, or extreme weather events.

The project BlueBird, however, deals with flexibility, rather than extreme external events. Therefore, it was decided to capture the improvement of the building's ability to respond flexibly to electricity demand and supply signals, thus enhancing its role as a stable, adaptive component of the broader energy system.

The following tables present the core KPIs, i.e., the ones that all pilots (except ENEA Grid Building) need to keep track of, for the social, the economic, and the technical dimension. Overall, the aim was to limit the number of KPIs to a level necessary to capture the status and development of the project without creating too much data and thus decrease the expressive power of the evaluation. Additionally, there are pilot specific KPIs which will be integrated into the documentation of the BlueBird pilots.

Table 1 Table 2 presents the social KPIs that were planned to be monitored as part of the proposal. The core idea was to measure both the acceptance towards flexibility solutions and different energy flexibility behaviors in the demo sites, as well as different components of the empowerment concept, i.e., indicating the level of empowerment perceived by people. Next to thermal comfort, which should ideally improve but most importantly not decrease due to new solutions; the empowerment assessment of inhabitants via surveys is based on the operationalization of the COM-B model of behaviour change, i.e., assessing motivation, capability and opportunity to show energy flexibility behaviors and use or accept related technologies. These aspects were planned to be measured through a survey with demo site inhabitants or employees, depending on the demo.

Table 2: Social Core Impact KPIs – as planned in the proposal

Social Core Impact KPIs – as planned in the proposal		
Name	Concept	Formula
Increased level of user acceptance	Monitor and increase user acceptance in demos	% of increase in level: Likert scale (surveys)
Increased acceptance of energy flex behaviour	Understand the determinants of acceptance of energy flex behaviour and operationalize these through survey questions	% of increase in level: Likert scale (surveys)
Perceived Comfort Level	Survey based on thermal preferences and thermal satisfaction, based on the ASHRAE standard 55-2017	% of increase in level: Likert scale (surveys)
Increased empowerment - Motivation	Mean percentage increase in indicators, e.g., belief in system benefits; reduced pluralistic ignorance; positive spillover to other sustainable technologies;	% of increase in level: Likert scale (surveys)
Increased empowerment – Capability	Mean percentage increase in indicators, e.g., adaptability of system to consumer needs; acceptance along diverse sample (diversity in	% of increase in level: Likert scale (surveys)

	gender, household size, socio-economic status), perceived level of control; perceived efficacy (individual / collective);	
Increased empowerment – Opportunity	Mean percentage increase in indicators, e.g., adaptability of system to consumer needs; acceptance along diverse sample (diversity in gender, household size, socio-economic status), perceived level of control; perceived efficacy (individual / collective);	% of increase in level: Likert scale (surveys)

However, a first analysis of the situations in the pilots revealed that parts of the original plan for assessment were not feasible. In order to achieve data that are scientifically robust, at least 50 participants would be needed per quantitative survey, and only two Pilots (AMB, ENEA Office Building) allow for such numbers of respondents. In these two pilots, which both mostly focus on implementing technical solutions which should be accepted, ideally not overridden and increase people’s comfort, we will assess the aforementioned KPIs in a survey as planned. In the other pilots, where residents will be empowered to become assets of building flexibility (e.g., KARNO), and employees are meant to interact actively with the system at least in the beginning (e.g., ENK), the numbers of respondents that are realistically accessible multiple times are well below the required number of participants. To combat the risk of not being able to assess meaningful results, it was therefore decided to use focus groups and semi-structured interviews, to generate more in-depth, qualitative insights that allow for an informative assessment. In detail, therefore, the social science team within BlueBird decided to proceed the following way that enables the pursuit of both above mentioned objectives:

- Semi-structured qualitative interviews in all Pilots with smaller samples, including some quantitative assessments within, that contain a subset of the original KPIs, although the latter will not yield statistically relevant results, but rather give a more in-depth and detailed indication of a direction of change for the sample sizes given.
- Re-using established contact points, e.g., focus groups that have already been created.
- Implement these interviews at 2 points in time instead of 3, describing a more in-depth change with people who are actually impacted through the project in some way.
- Maintain this procedure for all pilots with smaller sample sizes, to provide comparable results and detect differences in how people are affected among different pilots.
- Stick to the originally proposed method for the two Pilots who allow for larger sample sizes: AMB and ENEA.

The following tables summarize the Economic and Technical Core KPIs. It is worth to note that these are general definitions of the metrics; each pilot will implement them a bit differently depending on data availability and circumstances. For instance, regarding flexibility, different temporary requirements apply for each type of market or aggregator.

Table 3: Economic Core Impact KPIs

Economic Core Impact KPIs		
Name	Concept	Formula
Economic Resilience:	Resilience captures the reaction to an extreme external event.	$VOF = \frac{C_{no\ shift} - C_{with\ shift} + Reward_{shift}}{C_{no\ shift}}$

Value of Flexibility	Flexibility supports economic resilience in the case of price disturbances. The KPI VOF (value of flexibility) compares energy cost with vs. without flexibility	<p>Where:</p> $C_{no\ shift} = \text{total electricity expenditure (€) without smart control or load shifting}$ $C_{with\ shift} = \text{total electricity expenditure (€) with smart control (flexible pricing, if not real then modelled) or load shifting}$ $\text{Reward}_{shift} = \text{income from providing flexibility (€), based on Energy shifted}$
Economic Resilience: Cost Control	Resilience captures the reaction to an extreme external event. Flexibility supports economic resilience in the case of high price disturbances. The KPI represents the ability to keep energy cost low in such cases.	<p>“reduction of kWh expenses” or “reduction of energy cost per kWh due to shifting demand “</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - €/kWh grid price to be compared with - $\frac{€}{kWh} \text{ grid price} * \frac{\text{grid kWh}}{\text{total kWh}}$
Monthly Levelized Cost of Saved Energy	This energy cost measurement compares the cost of purchase and installation/deployment of smart products to extract energy flexibility against the energy cost savings	<p>Takes into account all benefits and costs of flexibility, e.g., optimised self-consumption.</p> $MLCSE = \frac{\text{monthly energy cost savings} + \text{reward} - \text{monthly investment annuity}}{\text{monthly energy savings}}$ $= \frac{(C_{no\ shift} - C_{with\ shift}) + \text{Reward}_{shift} - \sum_{sc=1}^z \left(I_{0sc} \times \frac{r_m(1+r_m)^{N_{msc}}}{(1+r_m)^{N_{msc}} - 1} \right)}{\text{monthly present value of total Energy Savings}}$ <p>Where</p> $C_{no\ shift} = \text{total electricity expenditure (€) without smart control or load shifting}$ $C_{with\ shift} = \text{total electricity expenditure (€) with smart control}$ $I_0 = \text{Initial investment (€)}$ $r_m = \text{Monthly discount rate} = \text{annual rate} / 12$ $N_m = \text{Lifetime in months (years} \times 12)$ $SC = \text{flexibility equipment (scope identified by pilot)}$

Table 4: Technical Core Impact KPIs

Technical Core Impact KPIs		
Name	Concept	Formula

Energy Savings	<p>An intuitive KPI asking for the energy consumption before and after an intervention or in the course of the project. It relates to total energy savings, but should be split also into savings relating to the usage of heat vs. savings of (other) electric equipment.</p>	<p>Energy savings relating to a period of time (formula 1) vs intervention-based (formula 2):</p> <p>1) $EnergySavings_{Temporal} := \frac{E_{Cons}^T}{E_{Cons}^{T-1}} * 100$</p> <p>2) $EnergySavings_{Intervention} := \frac{E_{Cons}^I}{E_{Cons}^{BL}} * 100$</p> <p>With:</p> <p>$E_{Cons}^T$ = Energy consumption at time T (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^{T-1} = Energy consumption at time T-1, i.e., the period before (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^I = Energy consumption after an intervention I (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^{BL} = Baseline BL energy consumption (kWh)</p>
Rebound Effect	<p>The rebound effect is both a technical and a social KPI, as it answers the question whether energy efficiency increases in one area might lead to an overall increased energy consumption.</p>	<p>Energy savings relating to a period of time (formula 1) vs intervention-based (formula 2):</p> <p>$Rebound_{Temporal} := E_{Cons}^T - E_{Cons}^{T-1} \geq 0$</p> <p>$Rebound_{Intervention} := E_{Cons}^I - E_{Cons}^{BL} \geq 0$</p> <p>With:</p> <p>$E_{Cons}^T$ = Energy consumption at time T (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^{T-1} = Energy consumption at time T-1, i.e., the period before (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^I = Energy consumption after an intervention I (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^{BL} = Baseline BL energy consumption (kWh)</p>
Ratio of CO₂ Savings	<p>Ratio of CO₂ savings is the only KPI that is relevant for EU climate targets and one of the ultimate goals of rendering buildings flexible. Here it is important to monitor and sum up all the time slots in a period, e.g., quarters of the hour, as</p>	<p>CO₂ savings comparing two consecutive time intervals (formula 1) vs intervention-based, which implies measurements during to possibly two non-consecutive intervals but some time before and after a particular intervention (formula 2):</p> <p>$CO_2_{Temporal} := \left(\frac{E_t \cdot Coeff_t}{E_{t-1} \cdot Coeff_{t-1}} \right) \cdot 100$</p> <p>$CO_2_{Intervention} := \sum \left(\frac{E_{Cons}^I}{E_{Cons}^{BL}} * CO_2_{Coeff}_t * 100 \right)$</p>

	<p>the CO₂-coefficient is time dependent.</p>	<p>With:</p> <p>E_{Cons}^{T0} = Energy consumption at beginning of monitoring period (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^{T-1} = Energy consumption at time T-1, i.e., the period before (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^I = Energy consumption after an intervention I (kWh)</p> <p>E_{Cons}^{BL} = Baseline (BL) energy consumption (kWh)</p> <p>$CO_2Coef f_t$ = Proportion of CO₂ per kilowatt hour, time dependent</p>
<p>Energy Flex: Increasing Load Shifting Capacity (ILSC)</p>	<p>ILSC is absolute amount of upwards shiftable power.</p>	$ILSC := \max(P_{BL} - P_{min})$ <p>With</p> <p>P_{BL} = Baseline Power Consumption without flexibility (KW)</p> <p>P_{min} = Minimum Power Consumption by maximally exploiting downwards flexibility (KW)</p>
<p>Energy Flex: Decreasing Load Shifting Capacity (DLSC)</p>	<p>DLSC is absolute amount of downwards shiftable power.</p>	$DLSC := (P_{max} - P_{BL})$ <p>With</p> <p>P_{BL} = Baseline Power Consumption without flexibility (KW)</p> <p>P_{max} = Maximum Power Consumption by maximally exploiting upwards flexibility (KW)</p>
<p>Energy Flex: Building Energy Flexibility Index (BEFI)</p>	<p>BEFI expresses relative flexibility in a building. In case of positive or negative values of the flexible power, there can be two versions of this metric.</p>	$BEFI := \frac{P_{flex}^I}{P_{Total}^{BL}} * 100$ <p>With:</p> <p>P_{flex}^I = Flexible power (KW), i.e. power that can be shifted to a different point in time</p> <p>E_{flex}^{BL} = Baseline power (KW)</p>
<p>Energy Flex: Energy flexibility EF</p>	<p>EF is the difference of power profiles between a baseline and power profile implementing flexibility. Here, the numeric value should</p>	$EF = \int_0^{t_{DR}} P_{e,DR} - P_{e,R} dt$ <p>With:</p> <p>$PP_{e,DR}$ = power profiles with flexibility (kWh)</p>

	be visualized by plotting the power profiles.	PP_{BL} = baseline power profiles (kWh)
Energy Flex: Reliability Performance Index	Reliability of flexibility (RPI) is a prerequisite for participation in many demand response programs and compares assessed/promised vs. realized flexibility	<p>With: $RPI_{Intervention} := \frac{P_{flex\ delivered}^I}{PP_{flex\ promised}^I} * 100$</p> <p>$E_{flex\ delivered}^I$ = flexibility delivered (kWh)</p> <p>$E_{flex\ promised}^I$ = flexibility promised (kWh)</p>

III.3. Process KPIs

Process KPIs will be monitored on pilot level and integrated in the documentation of the pilots' business cases. Apart from metrics that deal with countable items as e.g., the number of buildings using the BlueBird system or the amount of increased PV peak capacity this also applies to the monitoring of the smart readiness indicator SRI, which is the most important process KPI.

The reason for viewing the SRI as a process indicator is that it contains a set of services that offer the *potential to increase the flexibility* of a building. However, they are not the *building flexibility realized*, as this flexibility is only activated to the extent that the services are applied.

III.3.1. The BlueBird Smart Readiness Indicator

The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)² was introduced by EU entities to make smart readiness of buildings more comparable among buildings and to monitor development over time. It consists of a set of nine technical domains and seven impact criteria and huge set of smart service definitions arising from cross-applying these two dimensions. For each service, different levels of maturity are defined.

Still, BlueBird offers a set of services beyond the ones contained in the SRI. In order to analyze the difference, a mapping process was implemented. As a result, 8 BlueBird services were deemed to be covered by the SRI, but 12 additional flexibility extraction services were not included. It was then agreed to create a BlueBird version of the KPI spanning all services from the original SRI, but also including specific BlueBird services. The following Table 5 list the services added to the BlueBird SRI; the IDs are retained from the BlueBird DoA.

Table 5: Service Names

ID	Service Name (originating from DoA)
1	Historical data harmonization and assessment
3	Adaptive building models as input to model predictive control
4	Weather forecast optimized for the local conditions to be used as input to model predictive control

² https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator_en

5	Prediction of building's heating and cooling needs
8	Prediction of dynamic energy prices
9	Flexibility assessment on unit level
11	Models for predictive control of the ventilation
13	Smart-Charging services for EVs
15	Recommendations for manual control of heat
16	End-user interaction optimization service
18	Analysis of profits from DSR services (and potential energy savings)
20,1	Flexibility trade-off: internal vs. external flexibility
20,2	Flexibility trading service

Pilots need to monitor both, the original SRI and the BlueBird SRI at the beginning of the project – these can be found in the demo descriptions in Chapter IV – in the project's mid term, and at the end of the project.

IV. THE DEMOS DESCRIPTIONS: CONTEXT AND INFRASTRUCTURE, VISIONS, USE CASES, AND IMPLEMENTATION PLANS

The BlueBird journey started with a deep analysis of the demonstration sites to deep dive into the situational context of the future BlueBird system and its functionalities: Beyond the services defined in the DoA, what are the specific flavours in the demo sites, what are technical and social constraints and which data are available in which quality and granularity, and finally, what is the regulatory context in which such a system could be enacted?

Therefore, the demo descriptions reflect the situations in the pilot sites of roughly the first 6 months of the project. This also includes the SRIs and BlueBird SRIs which were developed until M4. Starting alongside these discussions UCs were defined, compared among the different demos, stream-lined into the UC system (see Chapter II) and reiterated to be instantiated into specific UCs for each demo case, which can be found as part of the demo descriptions in sections IV.x.5. They therefore represent the project status at around M9, i.e., in fall of 2025. Implementation plans (Sections IV.x.6) and the evaluation framework along with specific pilots' metrics and KPIs (Sections IV.x.7) were generated in step with the UCs in summer and reiterated in fall. A small paragraph was added to sections IV.x.6 to reflect the status of the implementation with reference to the original plans at M13. These sections also contain a graphic representing the current state of implementation for each pilot partner; the full implementation plan in table format can be found in the appendix.

IV.1. KARNO: Business Case Analysis Thermal Energy Grid for residentials

IV.1.1. General Business Case Information

IV.1.1.a. Buildings and Local Context

IV.1.1.a.1. Building 1: Type and features

The Profondeville (k-0001) site consists of four identical residential buildings (A, B, C, and D), each housing five apartments. These buildings are part of a thermal energy grid, designed to provide sustainable heating during winter and cooling during summer, as well as domestic hot water to the residents.

Figure 3: Apartment Plan

Each building follows the same structural design, ensuring **consistency in layout and energy distribution**. The apartments within each building are categorized by size, as outlined below:

Apartment Type	Identifier	Surface Area (m ²)
Type 1	0.1 (or 1)	93.20
Type 2	0.2 (or 2)	102.50
Type 3	1.1 (or 3)	100.40
Type 4	1.2 (or 4)	103.10
Type 5	2.1 (or 5)	147.00

As the buildings were completed in 2024, each apartment is highly energy efficient, with the buildings achieving the highest energy performance rating (PEB A or A+). The heating and cooling system relies on ground heaters for space heating, ensuring even and efficient thermal distribution. Domestic hot water is provided through classic household equipment, including showers, taps, and other standard fixtures.

IV.1.1.a.2. Local Context

The k-0001 site is located in a rural area, specifically in Profondeville, a village in the commune of Profondeville in the Province of Namur, within the Wallonia Region and the French Community of Belgium. This project marks the first thermal energy grid of Karno involving residential consumers and serves as a pilot for energy-efficient housing solutions.

The site is considered both a final product for Karno and a significant first real-world project where the company can observe the actual operation of the system in a residential setting. The thermal energy grid at k-0001 provides heating, cooling, and domestic hot water to all 20 apartments. The system is designed to maximize energy efficiency and cost savings, offering residents a low-carbon alternative to traditional

heating and cooling methods. The integration of local renewable energy sources, such as photovoltaic (PV) panels, will further reduce the site’s environmental impact as the project develops.

Figure 4: 3D Render of Pilot

IV.1.1.b. Current SRI

SRI, original EU version, M5 of the project: (Versus 32,5 % from proposal. The objective in the proposal is to reach 56,8 %)

Figure 5: KARNO SRI EU standard score card in the proposal

SRI BlueBird Version, M5 of the project:

Smart Readiness Indicator for Buildings

The SRI calculations have been performed with an experimental tool. Please note that the scores and the visual presentation of results are solely provided for testing purposes. Using this experimental tool can by no means lead to any claims on an actual score or certificate for a building.

SRI spreadsheet tool Version 4.5

Figure 6: KARNO BlueBird SRI score card at M5

IV.1.1.c. Stakeholders Overview

Below is the list of stakeholders, grouped by category:

- Stakeholder [Customers]: 20 clients (around 40 consumers)
- Stakeholder [Operational Actors]: Karno (Grid Devloper), Chaleur Verte Profondeville (Asset Owner), Karno Operations (DSO), Komfor (Supplier)
- Stakeholder [Operational Subcontractors]: Bevert (Maintenance subcontractor of Karno Operations), ZeroFriction (Client Services and Invoice subcontractor of Komfor)
- Stakeholder [Electricity Actors]: Eneco (Supplier) and Ores (DSO)
- Stakeholder [Regulatory Actor]: SPW Energie (Wallonia Administration)

IV.1.1.d. Legal Framework

The main regulatory framework governing this demonstration site is the thermal energy regional regulation. The relevant legislative texts can be accessed below:

- **Decree of the Walloon Government:** A legislative act passed by the Walloon Parliament that has the force of law within the Walloon Region. It establishes general rules and principles that must be followed in a specific sector, such as thermal energy regulations.

<https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/loi-decret/2020/10/15/2020204339>

- **Walloon Government Order:** A regulatory act issued by the Walloon Government (the regional executive body). It provides detailed implementation rules for a decree, specifying how it should be applied in practice.

<https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/arrete/2022/07/07/2022033704>

- **Ministerial Order:** A directive issued by a regional minister, often to clarify or update technical details within the framework of a government order. It is typically used for administrative or operational adjustments.

<https://wallex.wallonie.be/eli/arrete/2024/05/21/2024009509>

IV.1.2. Technical Infrastructure

IV.1.2.a. Heat

IV.1.2.a.1. Physical Infrastructure: Type of heating/cooling, energy sources, grid

The physical infrastructure is divided into six building blocks (BB).

BB1 represents the renewable heat source, which consists of a closed loop geothermal system with eight probes, each 100 meters deep.

BB2 is the (Centralized) Energy Center (EC), which houses a geothermal heat pump with a nominal power of 40 kW and an aerothermal heat pump with a nominal power of 20 kW. A 2m³ buffer tank is installed. In winter, both the geothermal and aerothermal heat pumps produce hot water for the network. In summer, the geothermal probes circulate cold water using a simple pump, while the aerothermal heat pump generates hot water to regenerate the geothermal probes. Below, on the left side, is an overview of the EC.

Figure 7: Overview of the Energy Center (EC) and Heating Network Layout

BB3 corresponds to the distribution network, which consists of two pipes per branch, one for supply and one for return. One branch connects Buildings 1 and 2 to the EC, while the other branch connects Buildings 3 and 4 to the EC. The supply temperature ranges between 30 and 35°C in winter and is around 20°C in summer. Behind on the right is a view of the network located between the EC and the buildings.

BB4 includes the common supply point and internal network. In apartment buildings like these, a common supply point exists between the building entrance and individual apartments. This section includes shared equipment, such as riser pipes. There is no hydraulic separation between the distribution network and the internal building network.

BB5 refers to the Heat Interface Unit (HIU), which is installed in each apartment. The HIU includes a small booster heat pump for domestic hot water production (water to water) and energy meters to separately measure hot domestic water consumption and heat emissions. A small tank of 120 liters or a bigger one of 200 liters is also installed in each apartment.

BB6 consists of the monitoring equipment. All parameters can be read in the EC and in the apartments. Furthermore, they can be adjusted in the EC.

IV.1.2.a.2. Energy mix for heating

In Profondeville, the energy mix supplied to consumers consists of two components: a geothermal heat pump integrated with an aerothermal heat pump.

The combination of these two sources enables better resource management. Geothermal heat extraction must remain within a specific temperature range to ensure long-term sustainability. On the other hand, the efficiency of the aerothermal heat pump is limited in winter when outdoor temperatures are low.

The sustainability of the geothermal resource is ensured by:

- The aerothermal heat pump acting as the primary heat source to reduce excessive underground energy extraction.
- Passive building cooling (free cooling) in summer: Heat extracted from buildings during cooling is used to regenerate geothermal wells.

- Active regeneration of geothermal wells in summer via the aerothermal heat pump: The system is designed to inject heat produced by the aerothermal heat pump back into the geothermal probes.

IV.1.2.a.3. What can be controlled?

The goal of Karno in Profondeville is to optimize the SCOP of the installation. The entire energy center is controllable through specifically designed scenarios. In practice, the parameters that can be adjusted are:

- The temperature and pressure setpoints of the heat pump, tank, and supply network.
- The start and stop timing of the heat pumps.
- The filling level of the tank.

The images below show the software used to control these parameters of the EC.

Figure 8: Energy Center Control Software: Production and Distribution Interface

IV.1.2.a.4. Data availability

Karno's goal on this site is to produce heat efficiently, with numerous sensors installed to monitor heat and cold energy production and consumption. Each apartment has an HIU with energy meters and a booster heat pump for domestic hot water (DHW) production.

A dedicated visualization dashboard is available (Figure 9: Performance Graph Karno), and historical data is stored on a cloud (Bigquery); data can be accessed via a Centralized Technical Management (CTM) system.

Figure 9: Performance Graph Karno

Table 6: Karno heating data description

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Heat data from the energy center	1 min	EC	1 hour (future: historic)	CTM --> API --> BigQuery (cloud)
Heat data from users	15 min	EC	1 hour (future: historic)	Individual counter --> CTM --> API --> BigQuery (cloud)

IV.1.2.b. Electricity

IV.1.2.b.1. Physical Infrastructure: Grid, PV installed, biomass

Karno's installations in Profondeville are connected to the electrical grid and to a local PV installation. The electricity is used mainly for the heat pumps (aerothermal and geothermal) and circulation pumps.

At the end of September 2025, photovoltaic panels with a nominal power of 41 kW were installed. These PV panels supply the EC (Energy Center) before injection to the energy community.

In the course of 2026, the pricing of the electricity from the grid will change from bi-hourly pricing (peak / offpeak) to hourly market price (day ahead).

Figure 10: Energy distribution Karno

IV.1.2.b.2. Energy mix for electricity

Before October 2025, the energy mix was 100% electricity from the grid. Since solar panels were added, the electricity mix in winter so far is around 10% (21/11/2025 to 28/01/2026). The goal is to optimize production during periods of high solar irradiance, high demand, and/or high grid prices.

IV.1.2.b.3. What can be controlled?

The geothermal heat pump and the heat pump used for the district heating are the electrical assets that can be controlled.

IV.1.2.b.4. Data availability

Table 7: Karno electricity data description

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Electricity consumption of the energy center (kWh)	15 min	EC	Historic (start 11/2024)	myOres
PV production	1 hour	CEC	Historic (start 21/11/2025)	Solar Fusion

IV.1.3. Social Infrastructure

IV.1.3.a. Stakeholders’ Goals, Drivers, and Barriers

IV.1.3.a.1. Customers:

Goals:

Customers aim to maintain their desired level of comfort while minimizing CO₂ emissions and reducing their energy expenses. They expect a reliable energy supply that does not compromise their quality of life while benefiting from cost savings through optimized energy consumption.

Drivers:

The potential for energy flexibility optimization can lead to a reduction in overall consumption and, consequently, lower energy bills. Additionally, customers may be motivated by sustainability goals and the opportunity to be part of an innovative energy model that supports decarbonization.

Barriers:

Customers need assurance that participating in flexibility efforts will not impact their comfort levels. Additionally, financial or service-based rewards must be attractive enough to justify their involvement in adapting consumption habits. A lack of familiarity with flexibility markets or energy management tools could also limit engagement.

IV.1.3.a.2. Operational Actors:

Goals:

Karno and its operational partners (Komfor and Karno Operations as sister companies) aim to optimize energy production and distribution while ensuring that the system remains robust, efficient, and easy to manage. Their objective is to balance cost-effectiveness with operational simplicity, ensuring a reliable supply for customers.

Drivers:

Reducing operational costs (mainly electricity consumption) enhances overall competitiveness while simultaneously lowering CO₂ emissions. The integration of renewable energy sources, such as photovoltaics (PV), and participation in flexibility markets present opportunities to increase efficiency and sustainability.

Barriers:

Flexibility participation might introduce operational complexity that needs to be carefully managed. The challenge is to ensure a sufficient level of interest and engagement (for example: currently, Karno operates under a variable electricity contract with peak and off-peak pricing, allowing a limited degree of optimization).

IV.1.3.a.3. Operational Subcontractor:

These stakeholders do not have direct goals related to the BlueBird project, so their objectives are framed within the broader context of the thermal energy grid and supply.

Goals:

- **ZeroFriction** seeks to automate and standardize invoicing, payments, administrative work, and customer interactions as much as possible to improve efficiency and reduce manual workload.
- **Bever** focuses on improving maintenance and enhancing the robustness of the infrastructure to ensure long-term reliability.

Drivers:

Both subcontractors are driven by cost reduction and operational simplification. Standardized and automated processes can help them optimize resources and improve service quality.

Barriers:

The need for highly customized solutions adds complexity to their operations. Both companies work across multiple energy networks, making them hesitant towards solutions that are not scalable or require significant adaptation for each case. Ensuring compatibility with their existing workflows is essential.

IV.1.3.a.4. Electricity Actors:

Goals:

Electricity supplier and the distribution system operator (DSO) aim to encourage Karno to consume electricity in a more flexible way (adapting consumption to align with grid needs). By shifting demand to periods of excess supply, they can improve grid stability and efficiency.

Drivers:

A more flexible consumption pattern can lead to cost reductions for both the electricity supplier (who is supporting our consumer profile risk) and the DSO (by leveraging Karno's ability to adjust energy usage, they can optimize grid management and integrate more renewable energy sources without overloading the system).

Barriers:

The presence of PV generation on Karno's side may not be beneficial for these actors, as it reduces Karno's reliance on purchased electricity. This could limit the financial incentives for suppliers and DSOs to actively support Karno's flexibility efforts. Additionally, incorporating PV generation into the system increases complexity in managing energy flows and forecasting demand.

IV.1.3.a.5. Regulatory Actors:

Goals:

Regulatory authorities aim for BlueBird to develop an efficient and viable business model that reduces CO₂ emissions and increases flexibility, ultimately supporting the clean energy transition in Wallonia. The goal is to create a replicable framework that can be used as a reference for similar projects.

Drivers:

A successful and scalable business case would help regulators refine policies and evolve energy regulations to support innovative energy models. By demonstrating the feasibility of energy flexibility and decentralized energy systems, BlueBird can contribute to shaping future regulatory frameworks that encourage clean energy adoption.

Barriers:

Regulators must ensure that customers remain well protected in new energy models. This includes safeguarding fair pricing, contract transparency, and reliability of service. Balancing innovation with consumer protection measures is a key challenge in regulatory evolution.

IV.1.3.b. Current Stakeholder Communication Setup

Below, you will find a diagram illustrating the communication flow between stakeholders, followed by an explanation of each communication setup:

Figure 11: Communication Setup Karno

1. Internal communication takes place between the Operational Actors within Karno's companies. This is considered internal company communication, including meetings, calls, emails, messaging platforms, and shared information systems.
2. The communication between Karno Operations and Bevert follows a subcontractor relationship model. Exchanges primarily occur through emails, messaging platforms, and calls, with meetings being rare.
3. The third communication flow exists between Komfor and the Electricity Actors—Eneco (supplier) and Ores (DSO). In this case, Komfor acts as a client, communicating through dedicated online portals (one for Eneco and another for Ores). Additionally, Komfor has direct contact points for specific inquiries, which are handled via emails, calls, and meetings when necessary.
4. The communication flow between Zero Friction and Komfor also follows a subcontractor relationship model. Their exchanges occur through recurring meetings, calls, emails, and shared platforms.
5. Communication between Komfor and the Customers is limited and typically occurs only for specific requests or during the initial setup phase. Komfor aims to minimize direct interactions and instead prioritizes communication via the next channel.
6. The main communication flow between Zero Friction and the Customers is dedicated to customer service. Exchanges take place via a customer portal, document sharing, call centers, emails, and other digital communication tools. If Komfor needs to send specific information to customers, it will generally request Zero Friction to handle it. However, if the request falls outside Zero Friction's scope, Komfor will communicate directly with the customers. This makes the communication flow between Zero Friction and the Customers the primary communication channel between customers and the Operational Actors.

7. The Regulator primarily communicates through its website, where it publishes regulatory texts and updates. When necessary, the Operator (Karno Operations) and the Supplier (Komfor), as the main concerned entities, can directly engage with the regulator through email exchanges to ask questions or discuss specific regulatory matters.

IV.1.3.c. Current Social Fabric

Currently, the only social fabric among consumers is their shared geographic location, as they live in the same area, share some common spaces, and are all connected to the thermal energy grid.

In the future, with the installation of PV panels, an administrative fabric will emerge through the formation of an Energy Community, bringing together Komfor and all consumers.

IV.1.4. Vision

The Profondeville project aims to demonstrate the economic, environmental, and social value of a decentralized thermal energy grid in a residential setting. By integrating energy-efficient buildings, renewable energy sources, and smart consumption strategies, the project will reduce CO₂ emissions, lower energy costs, and enhance consumer awareness of energy use. Also, by leveraging energy flexibility across multiple vectors (thermal and electrical), the project not only ensures optimal heating and cooling efficiency but also explores how the hybrid system can actively contribute to the electricity grid's stability and efficiency.

This vision extends beyond infrastructure deployment; it seeks to create a scalable and replicable model for flexible energy management, leveraging consumer participation and real-time demand response. Through occupant-driven flexibility and energy-sharing mechanisms, the project will enhance thermal grid efficiency, support renewable thermal energy integration, and foster stronger community engagement in sustainable energy solutions.

IV.1.4.a. Technical Building Flexibility

The thermal energy grid at Profondeville will optimize energy consumption by leveraging predictive control strategies and real-time flexibility mechanisms. By integrating photovoltaic (PV) self-consumption optimization, the system will dynamically adjust heating and cooling loads based on:

- Aerothermal and geothermal heating and cooling, balancing energy demand with optimal seasonal performance.
- Solar PV self-consumption, aligning heating and cooling loads with solar production to minimize grid reliance.
- Thermal storage capabilities to shift energy consumption and improve efficiency.

By leveraging these flexibility mechanisms, the project will demonstrate how hybrid energy systems can actively participate in energy markets while providing optimal comfort and cost savings for residents.

IV.1.4.b. Social Building Flexibility

The success of occupant-driven energy flexibility requires an engaged and informed user base. The project will implement targeted communication strategies to encourage energy-saving behaviours and participation in demand-side management.

Key initiatives include:

- Real-time feedback tools to help residents understand and optimize their energy use.
- Behavioural science-based interventions to encourage proactive energy-saving actions.
- Community-level engagement strategies to foster a sense of collective energy responsibility.

- Rebound-sensitive communication to prevent unintended increases in consumption due to perceived energy savings.

By empowering residents to make informed choices, the project will strengthen social cohesion and enable cost savings through adaptive consumption habits.

IV.1.4.c. Technical Infrastructure

The Karno site is fully integrated into a smart energy ecosystem, interacting with grid operators, digital platforms, and flexibility markets to:

- Optimize hybrid system efficiency, balancing aerothermal, geothermal, and PV production.
- Integration with grid flexibility markets, demonstrating the economic potential of hybrid systems as demand-response assets.
- Enhance storage utilization, ensuring strategic energy retention and release for maximum self-consumption.
- Provide demand-side flexibility, adjusting consumption patterns to reduce peak loads and increase renewable integration.
- Expand district heating feasibility, assessing technical and economic conditions for future network growth.

By demonstrating how multiple buildings can function as an integrated, demand-responsive energy hub, the project will establish a scalable model for residential thermal energy grids, bridging the gap between decentralized energy production and large-scale flexibility services.

IV.1.4.d. Social Infrastructure

Beyond technological advancements, Profondeville Thermal Grid is a model for community-based energy governance, fostering an inclusive and cooperative framework where residents, energy providers, and regulators collaborate to maximize the benefits of demand-side flexibility.

By aligning policy frameworks, stakeholder incentives, and user engagement, the project will:

- Ensure regulatory compliance, supporting the development of legal frameworks for hybrid energy flexibility.
- Encourage transparent energy governance, fostering trust and participation from residents.
- Demonstrate economic, social, and environmental benefits, paving the way for future municipal-scale energy flexibility initiatives.

By integrating hybrid energy technologies, behavioral strategies, and system-wide flexibility, Karno's site will serve as a blueprint for the future of district heating, reinforcing decentralized energy networks as key enablers of the clean energy transition.

IV.1.5. Use Cases

Figure 12: UC Overview: Karno

UC 1.1 Energy Consumption Prediction and Forecast of PV Harvest

'Provide a Day – ahead load curve of the hybrid energy system (aerothermal, geothermal, storage and user consumption). Forecasting PV harvest. With the aim of maximising the efficiency and effectiveness of energy systems considering the underground annual energy balance.

UC 1.2 Cost Optimization and Control of Hybrid Heat Energy Systems as a Tool for Grid Integration

Use the Digital Twin to optimize the system operation by costs, Operation for next day 24h; the pricing for consumer: each kWh for consumers is "sold" at a fixed price/kWh

UC 1.3 Cost Optimization to Generate Information for Recommendations

Optimisation and control of hybrid heat energy (combining aerothermal and geothermal) on top of UC1.2 to generate information for user recommendations

UC 1.4 Tool for Heat-based End-user Adaptation

Create a tool for End users behaviour adaptation as a means for heat grid integration - Scheduling the use of hot water, scheduling room heating via thermostat for pre-heating, delaying, (account for inertia: floor heating!). Assumption: aggregated demand remains the same in terms of sum of kWh is constant compared to DT simulation/prediction.

UC 1.5 Heat Grid Extension Study

Study potential expansion of the district heating network. Considering the feasibility and benefits of expanding the infrastructure to reach more areas, thereby increasing accessibility to renewable energy sources and flexibility potential.

Overall optimization (technical + behavioural) of heat grid extension to avoid increase of capacity constraint of grid connection and minimize depletion of ground heat source

IV.1.6. Implementation Plan and Current State of Implementation

Here is an excerpt from the implementation plan until beginning of February 2026; the full implementation plan can be found in the appendix.

Figure 13: Karno implementation plan timeline

Current state of Implementation

Business modelling and KPI definition have been implemented on time (WP2). However, there is a risk as the modelling of the site via a DT and the forecasting has not yet taken place (WP3). For a user interaction tool, focus group has taken place and some requirements have been collected (WP4/WP6), however, the extension of the KARNO interaction toolset is not ready yet and no experiment has been defined. The preparatory phase, as indicated in the last part of the implementation plan, has been successfully completed.

This situation carries a risk, as there is only one winter left for the demo to implement heat-based experiments. Fortunately, experiments in summer with the cooling functionality of the heat grid might still be implemented on time.

IV.1.7. Pilot Specific KPIs

Table 8: Karno: Pilot specific KPIs

ID	Name	Formula	Temporal Granularity
KARNO 1	Cost of Energy Supplied (€/MWh)	Electricity cost of the system / Supplied Thermal Energy	Daily – monthly – quarterly - annually
KARNO 2	PV Self consumption	Electricity consumed from the PV / Total Electricity consumed	Daily – monthly – quarterly - annually
KARNO 3	Investment saved	$(\text{CAPEX}_{\text{opt}} - \text{CAPEX}_{\text{ini}}) / \text{CAPEX}_{\text{ini}}$ - CAPEX_opt = capex to connect X kW more to the network with the optimization - CAPEX_ini = capex to connect X kW more to the network without the optimization (initially) - X (kw) = capacity saved thanks to the optimization (UC 1.5)	Project (once)
KARNO 4	Final user Empowerment in percent	Total number of final users receiving the flexibility requests/all KARNO inhabitants	Monthly
KARNO 5	Final user Acceptance	Proportion of flexibility requests successfully implemented relative to the total number of empowered final users.	Monthly

IV.2. AMB: PV self-consumption optimization and occupant-driven flexibility of public buildings on the Iberian electricity trading markets

IV.2.1. General Business Case Information

IV.2.1.a. Buildings and Local Context

IV.2.1.a.1. Sports Center building (IEB) – Illa Esportiva in Castellbisbal

Located in the town of Castellbisbal, the first building is a sports centre with an indoor swimming pool, gymnasium, fitness rooms, locker rooms area and offices, amongst other.

Equipment type summary:

- Electricity-driven chillers (2 cooling systems)
- 2 gas boilers for space heating (120 kW)
- 4 V1G EV chargers (2 of them have 22 kW each, and the other 2 have a power of 7,4 kW each).
- 2 PV power plants (1 rooftop PV system of 97,8 kWp; 1 PV system in the EV car park of 10 kWp).
- Domestic Hot Water tanks.
- Building management system and energy monitoring system. This sports centre has an indoor heated pool and sauna, humidity control devices for the pool and the sauna, pumping machines and Domestic Hot Water production.

The building's annual consumption is 627,30 MWh, and the overall annual PV generation is 133,024 MWh.

Energy carriers: Electricity and gas. Synergies with non-energy carriers: e-mobility.

Figure 14: Aerial view on Illa Esportiva - Castellbisbal

IV.2.1.a.2. Civic Centre building (CCB) – Centre Cívic Virgínia Amposta in Sant Vicenç dels Horts

The second building is the Civic Centre Virgina Amposta, which is located in Sant Vicenç dels Horts. It is a civic centre with a multipurpose hall (used for e.g. conference, theatre, concerts...), and with meeting rooms, activities rooms, etc.

Equipment type summary:

- Heat pump SH and SC (306 kW (heating)/277 kW (cooling)).
- Cool and hot storage tanks for the HVAC distribution system.
- Air handling units.
- Building Management System with remote control.
- The building's annual consumption is 200 MWh.
- Energy carriers: Electricity.

Figure 15: Aerial view on Centre Cívic Virgínia Amposta - Sant Vicenç dels Horts (CCVA)

IV.2.1.a.3. City Town building (MB) – Casa de la Vila in Montcada i Reixac

The third building is the Casa de la Vila, located in Montcada i Reixac. It is the village's old town hall. It is a lively space where, among other activities, workshops, courses, and exhibitions are held, as well as the plenary sessions of the consistory. This facility also houses the Municipal Museum, the Women's Service Office, the Local Catalan Service, the Justice of the Peace and the Councillor for Culture.

Equipment type summary:

- Variable refrigerant flow (VRF) System for cooling and heating, from Mitsubishi.
- Building Management System with remote control
- Electric meters for measuring separately the whole building's consumption and all the external units' electric consumption.
- Possibility of creating an energy community between this building and a nearby school with all the rooftops covered by PV panels.

The diversity of uses and schedules inside the building provides a challenging test building with more than 30 climatized spaces.

The annual electricity consumption of this building is 161.613 kWh/year.

Figure 16: View of Casa de la Vila – Montcada i Reixac

IV.2.1.b. Local Context

The Barcelona Metropolitan Area (AMB) is the public administration of the metropolitan territory of Barcelona, with an area of 636 km² and 36 municipalities with a population of over 3,2 million. It is the largest metropolitan agglomeration in the western Mediterranean and generates half of Catalonia's region GDP. The AMB has powers in the areas of social cohesion, territorial and urban planning, mobility, transport, waste management, water supply, environment protection, social housing, infrastructures and economic promotion in the metropolitan territory. Under the Climate&Energy Plan 2030, the organisation carries out actions to promote a process of transition towards a decentralised energy model based on renewable and sustainable energy with an integrated approach. The organisation has a sound experience in managing and implementing local and European projects in the fields of sustainable development, energy efficiency and economic, social and territorial cohesion, with specific focus on energy transition and fight against fuel poverty.

The supramunicipal vision of AMB is key to the implementation of pilot experiences, with a high potential for replicability among its 36 municipalities, which is conducted through the Metropolitan Board for a New Energy Model, a forum that gathers all the stakeholders of the territory helping to accelerate energy transition all across the metropolitan municipalities. Moreover, AMB owns Barcelona Energia, the metropolitan public utility that sells electricity to municipalities, public entities and private consumers, with a 100% green energy perspective, and specific care for fuel poverty situations. It also aims to become a technical, financial and awareness booster in order to increase the investments on energy transition on both public and private sector.

IV.2.1.c. Current SRI

SRI in Proposal: 30,34%

Max SRI expected in proposal: **78,49%**

IV.2.1.c.1. Sports Centre building (IEB) – Illa Esportiva in Castellbisbal

SRI BlueBird Version at M5 in the project: 24,8%

SRI original EU version v4.5 at M5 in the project: 23,1%

Figure 17: AMB IEB BlueBird SRI score card at M5

Figure 18: AMB IEB SRI EU standard score card in the proposal

IV.2.1.c.2. Civic Centre building (CCB) – Centre Cívic Virgínia Amposta in Sant Vicenç dels Horts

SRI BlueBird Version at M5 in the project: **19,04%**

SRI original EU version v4.5 version at M5 in the project: **32,5%**

Figure 19: AMB CCB BlueBird SRI score card at M5

Figure 20: AMB CCB SRI EU standard score card in the proposal

IV.2.1.c.3. City Town Building (MB) – Casa de la Vila in Montcada i Reixac

SRI BlueBird Version at M5 in the project: **18,20%**

SRI original EU version v4.5 version at M5 in the project: **9,7%**

Figure 21: AMB MB BlueBird SRI score card at M5

IV.2.1.d. Stakeholder Overview

- Barcelona Energia (TERSA) [Public Energy Supplier]
- Local Council of Castellbisbal
- Local Council of Sant Vicenç dels Horts
- Local Council of Montcada i Reixac
- CIMNE
- Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona (AMB)
- Building energy managers
- Building workers
- Building users for activities, classes or sports facilities
- EV Chargers users

IV.2.1.e. Legal Framework

GENERAL

- Royal Decree 314/2006, of March 17, which approves the Technical Building Code (Official State Gazette No. 74, March 28, 2006), including subsequent amendments.
- Law 34/2007, of November 15, on Air Quality and Atmospheric Protection (Official State Gazette No. 275, November 16, 2007), including subsequent amendments.

ELECTRICITY

- Low Voltage Electrotechnical Regulation (REBT) and its Complementary Technical Instructions (ITC BT). Royal Decree 842/2002, of August 2, issued by the Ministry of Science and Technology (Official State Gazette No. 224, September 18, 2002).
- Royal Decree 1890/2008, of November 14, approving the Regulation on Energy Efficiency in Outdoor Lighting Installations and its Complementary Technical Instructions.

Operating Procedures (Red Eléctrica de España - REE):

- P.O.7.2: Secondary regulation
 - P.O.7.3: Tertiary regulation
 - P.O.3.3: Activation of balancing energy from the Replacement Reserve product (RR)
 - P.O.3.2: Technical Constraints
- Royal Decree-Law 17/2022, of September 20, urgent measures in the field of energy, regarding the application of the remuneration scheme to cogeneration facilities, and temporarily reducing the Value Added Tax (VAT) rate applicable to the supply, import, and intra-community acquisition of certain fuels.

HVAC and DHW

- Royal Decree 178/2021, of March 23, amending Royal Decree 1027/2007, of July 20, which approves the Regulation on Thermal Installations in Buildings (RITE) and its Complementary Technical Instructions (IT), and establishes the Advisory Commission for Thermal Installations in Buildings.
- Royal Decree 865/2003, of July 4 (Official State Gazette No. 171, July 18, 2003), establishing the hygienic-sanitary criteria for the prevention and control of Legionellosis.
- Royal Decree 138/2011, of February 4, approving the Safety Regulation for Refrigeration Installations and its Complementary Technical Instructions.

IV.2.2. Technical Infrastructure

IV.2.2.a. Building1: Castellbisbal Sports Centre

IV.2.2.a.1. Heat

The main heating production in the building consist in two gas boilers located in the basement. They are used for the heating of the main rooms, for the production of Domestic Hot Water (DHW) and also for the heating of the indoor swimming pool water.

There are no options in heat flexibility due the heat production is done by gas.

IV.2.2.a.2. Electricity

Physical Infrastructure:

The building has three electrical connections:

- Grid
- Photovoltaic plant on the roof (97,8 kWp)

- Photovoltaic plant on the EV car park (10 kWp)

The building has electric meters for assessing the electrical consumption of the whole building and for the PV power generation.

In this building we will use electricity flexibility in for heating water of the Domestic Hot Water (DHW) system tanks or for pre-heating the water of the indoor swimming pool. Thus, we will save gas consumption by the boilers when flexibility electricity energy is available.

For heating the water of DHW there will be installed two electrical resistances into the hot water tanks, in order to heat the water using electricity when it is available.

For the pre-heating of the water of the swimming pool an aérothermal heat pump system will be installed, for heating the water using also electricity.

Finally, in the EV charging station we will play with social flexibility. A two lights (green and red) awareness system will be installed with the idea of informing users when it is a good moment for charging the vehicle or not.

What can be controlled?

To enhance the building's flexibility, the pilot implemented a heat pump for swimming pool heating and installed electric heaters in the domestic hot water (DHW) storage tanks. These measures enable electric load flexibility while reducing the building's reliance on gas consumption.

Moreover, a new control system it will be installed for manage all the new equipment, for monitorize these facilities and for sending and receiving data from the outside. Thus, this new system could be independent of building management system of the rest of facilities of the building.

In the next figure we can see what to be controlled:

Figure 22: Inputs and outputs in Illa Castellbisbal

Data availability

Table 9: AMB data availability: Illa Castellbisbal

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Electric consumption (kwh)	1'	Building	All the year	BMS

Energy price (€)	15'	Electrical market	All the year	TM
Setpoint temperatures (°C)	1'	Building	All the year	BMS
Water Temperatures (°C)	1'	Building	All the year	BMS
EV Chargers consumption	1'	Parking	All the year	Charging System

IV.2.2.a.3. EV chargers

Physical Infrastructure:

- There are 4 V1G EV chargers (2 of them have 22 kW each, and the other 2 have a power of 7,4 kW each).

Energy sources and energy mix for electricity

- The EV chargers are powered from the main switch board of the building.

What can be controlled?

At the moment, there is no control charging system. Due to the EV charge control being locked by the manufacturer, and there is no chance of directly activating it, it is opted to add some visual signals for the users to know when it is more favourable to charge the EVs.

IV.2.2.b. Technical Infrastructure Building II: Centre Civic Virgínia Amposta (Sant Vicenç dels Horts)

IV.2.2.b.1. Heat

Physical Infrastructure

All HVAC systems of the buildings are electricity driven. There is no gas supply.

Heat and Cool production are done by a Heat Pump of 306 kW Heating power and 277 kW cooling power.

There are two main inertial storage water tanks (hot and cold water) that work as a buffer for supplying hot or cold water to the indoor units which are fan coils or AHUs.

In this building there is not any PV system neither any EV charger, so all the flexibility is thought in terms of heat, although energy price will also take into account.

In the next figure we can see the HVAC scheme:

Figure 23: AMB HVAC system schematic

What can be controlled?

There is already installed a Building Management System (BMS) with remote control in the building for managing all the HVAC systems. At this moment we are working on getting access to the remote control and exploring how to collect and send data.

In the next figure we can see what to be controlled:

Figure 24: Inputs and outputs in Civic Center Virginia Amposta

Data availability

Table 10: Data availability AMB: Civic Center Virginia Amposta

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Electric consumption (kwh)	1'	Building	All the year	BMS

Energy price (€)	15'	Electrical market	All the year	TM
Temperatures (°C)	1'	Building	All the year	BMS
Setpoint temperatures (°C)	1'	Building	All the year	BMS
CO2 (ppms)	1'	Building	All the year	BMS

IV.2.2.c. Technical Infrastructure Building III: Casa de la Vila - Montcada i Reixac

IV.2.2.c.1. Electricity

Physical Infrastructure:

The building is connected to the grid with no energy generation. The main electric consumption is the HVAC system.

In 2024 the building energy consumption reached a maximum 5-minute consumption of 100kW. The 2024 building consumption is 139.000 kWh.

Figure 25: Total energy consumption and total HVAC consumption (hourly)

Also, in 2024, the maximum HVAC electric consumption reached a maximum 5-minute consumption of 78kW. The 2024 HVAC electricity consumption is 68.000 kWh.

What can be controlled?

All the HVAC systems can be remotely controlled at the thermostat level in this building. This control includes the temperature setpoint, status, fan speed and Operation Mode for all 30 climatization zones within the building.

Data availability

Table 11: Data availability AMB: Casa de la Vila

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
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Building electric consumption (kwh)	5'	Building	2 years	BMS
HVAC electric consumption (kwh)	5'	Building	2 years	BMS
Energy price (€)	15'	Electrical market	2 years	TM
Internal temperatures (°C)	5'	Each climatization zone	2 years	BMS
Setpoint temperatures (°C)	5'	Each climatization zone	2 years	BMS
Climatization status (ON/OFF)	5'	Each climatization zone	2 years	BMS
Splits Fan speed	5'	Each climatization zone	2 years	BMS
Weather	1h	Meteorological station	2 years	Meteo service

IV.2.3. Social Infrastructure

IV.2.3.a. Stakeholders' Goals, Drivers, and Barriers

To analyse the social infrastructure of the AMB pilot, building occupants are classified into two main groups according to the building typology and their duration of stay.

In Illa Castellbisbal Sports Centre and the Civic Centre Virginia Amposta, occupants mainly consist of visitors who stay in the building for limited periods while carrying out specific activities such as sports or cultural events. In contrast, the Casa de la Vila also accommodates office workers who remain in the building for extended periods, often throughout the full working day.

This distinction is relevant for the implementation of energy flexibility measures, since comfort expectations, operational dependence on building systems, and potential responsiveness to control strategies differ significantly between short-term users and permanent staff.

IV.2.3.a.1. Workers:

Goals:

Workers mainly expect stable indoor comfort conditions, especially regarding temperature and ventilation, during the whole working day. For this reason, flexibility measures should not reduce their comfort. If some adjustments are required, the purpose of these actions should be clearly explained, particularly in the relation of energy efficiency and sustainability.

Drivers:

Workers can support the project if they are properly informed about the planned measures. Communication campaigns will therefore explain the objectives of the project and encourage simple practices, such as charging electric vehicles at suitable times or keeping reasonable temperature setpoints.

Barriers:

Comfort remains the main concern for this group. If workers perceive that indoor conditions worsen, complaints may appear. It is therefore important to monitor feedback and address any issues in order to maintain acceptable working conditions.

IV.2.3.a.2. Users:

Goals:

As user comfort in these buildings is not as critical as it is for workers who are exposed for longer periods, the main objective in this case is to encourage users to engage with flexibility measures. This will be achieved by informing them and promoting good practices to follow.

In addition, further initiatives will be explored, such as offering fee reductions or other incentives to users who access the building during the most appropriate hours.

Drivers:

Provide clear information to users about the flexibility project and encourage them to actively participate in it.

Barriers:

Take into account any potential complaints received from users and address them appropriately.

IV.2.3.a.3. BCN Energia:

Goals:

Barcelona Energía is the metropolitan electricity supplier of Barcelona. As an energy retailer, it has extensive technical expertise in electricity market regulation. In its role as supplier for the assets under analysis, it has access to all relevant data from both the system operator and the market operator, enabling comprehensive monitoring and assessment of system performance.

Drivers:

This initiative represents an opportunity to further develop expertise in the flexibility market, paving the way to deliver similar services across the broader portfolio served by Barcelona's public electricity supplier.

Barriers:

The current regulatory framework, together with pending updates and its limited adaptability to specific use cases, may constrain the deployment and scalability of certain energy solutions.

IV.2.3.b. Current Stakeholder Communication Setup

Each building has on-site maintenance staff, as well as technical management provided by City Council personnel. All of them have access to information from the Building Management System (BMS) and other relevant building data. From AMB, communication is maintained directly with the teams at all buildings, who in turn liaise with workers and users at each facility.

In addition, AMB, CIMNE and Barcelona Energia maintain direct coordination among themselves. AMB and CIMNE also collaborate with external companies responsible for implementing the necessary BMS upgrades required to operate the flexibility project.

Finally, throughout the project, interaction with workers and users will be ensured through feedback mechanisms aimed at assessing acceptable comfort levels and overall acceptance of the new measures.

IV.2.3.c. Current Social Fabric (e.g., sports groups, energy communities...)

There are no formal stakeholder groups actively involved at present. However, for social analysis purposes, we consider the following groups: workers from Casa de la Vila and users from both Casa de la Vila and Centre Cívic Virgina Amposta.

For the Illa Esportiva building, users are more heterogeneous. While they can be subdivided based on the type of sport practiced, we do not treat these as separate groups and instead include them collectively under the general “users” category.

IV.2.4. Vision

Developing these pilot projects in three buildings within the Barcelona Metropolitan Area can serve as a model for scaling up to other buildings across different municipalities. As the region increasingly integrates renewable energy sources and demand-side electrification, implementing flexibility measures will become essential.

These measures can take a technological form, such as enhancing automation within building systems, or a social form, by raising awareness among citizens about energy flexibility and encouraging active participation.

IV.2.4.a. Technical Building Flexibility

Communication modules and control devices will be installed in the pilot buildings to collect operational and consumption data. This data will be analyzed through simulations, enabling the provision of instructions necessary to adjust the building’s energy demand in response to market conditions and photovoltaic production.

The primary systems targeted for intervention include photovoltaic generation, air conditioning, domestic hot water, ventilation systems, electric vehicle chargers, and other related building services

IV.2.4.b. Social Building Flexibility

Communication campaigns will be conducted to inform users about energy flexibility and how they can contribute through specific actions.

At Illa Esportiva in Castellbisbal, a visual awareness system will be installed at the electric vehicle charging station.

Additionally, satisfaction surveys will be carried out, and any complaints received will be collected and considered to inform the implementation of new flexibility measures within the buildings

IV.2.4.c. Technical Infrastructure

The long-term objective is to scale the solutions successfully implemented in the pilot buildings to other buildings across the Barcelona Metropolitan Area. Implementing flexibility measures will enable buildings to adjust their energy demand in response to grid conditions, which are increasingly influenced by the integration of renewable energy sources, particularly photovoltaic generation.

IV.2.4.d. Social Infrastructure

The experience gained from this project will support the development of social flexibility measures, which can be incorporated into future environmental education programs organized by the AMB.

IV.2.5. Use Cases

Figure 26: UC Overview: AMB

UC 2.1 Predict energy demand from municipal buildings and it's PV generation and the required forecasts for the predictions

Consumption prediction and needed forecasts from the tertiary buildings of the AMB. From the 3 diferent buildings are going to be modelled:

- Castellbisbal Sports Centre (Illa esportiva Castellbisbal): DT of electric heat for the swimming pool and DHW (devices to be installed), the PV installed on the rooftop and the EV Charging Station.
- Centre Cívic Virgínia Amposta (Sant Vicenç dels Horts): DT of Building with HVAC + forced ventilation.
- Casa de la Vila (Montcada i Reixac): DT of HVAC system + PV.

UC 2.2 Optimize Energy Cost of the Distributed Energy Resources

Model Predictive Control (MPC) of space heating/cooling and DHW systems, EV charger systems, and PV to reduce energy cost of the buildings under day ahead market and intraday prices. BE has control over the municipal buildings/assets from the AMB pilot. The general procedure is to source part of the electricity needed for the next day on the day-ahead market (for the next day) and source the rest from the intra-day market. For the day ahead market prices are known for each hour of the next day before 2 pm; for the intraday markets: 1. between 14h-15h there is a time-slot to operate in the market and buy electricity for each 15 minute slot of the next day; 2. between 21h-22h there is a time-slot to operate in the market for

the next day (same as before); market 3. from 9h-10h there is a timeslot to source electricity for 14h-24h. The market price will be a composite price combining the different markets considering the price and the relative amount of energy bought from each market.

The upper and lower flexibility limits will be constrained by the active participation of the building's occupants (get acceptance for a range of temperatures for the rooms heating).

The EV charging system has no direct actuation capabilities. Therefore, a user interaction strategy will be deployed to modify the consumption patterns by interacting with the users.

UC 2.3 Promote explicit flexibility market tailored to the Iberian electricity markets

The use case will optimise the operation of the building and the e-mobility-connected systems by exploiting the local generation and storage synergies to reduce the overall electricity cost. The upper and lower flexibility limits will be constrained by the active participation of the building's occupants (get acceptance for a range of temperatures for the rooms heating).

This use case will enhance the understanding and use of local flexibility, fostering a more dynamic and responsive electricity pricing mechanism. It will focus on emulating the aggregated participation of similar public buildings in one frequency and power regulation band, such as the tertiary band, to reduce electricity cost and help to stabilize the grid. The impact analysis will compare to the results of UC2.2 and decide on which market to use at which point in time: implicit vs explicit DR.

The regulation is currently being adapted to comply with market requirements under **Royal Decree 88/2026 of 11 February 2026**, approving the General Regulation on electricity supply, commercialization, and aggregation, which introduces the role of the independent demand aggregator. Further regulatory publications are expected to define and clarify its practical implementation within the electricity markets. The new market rules are impacted by the big black out in spring 2025 - the objective is to source more flexibility for regulation power.

Every day, the TSO publishes the forecast for consumption for the next day, being updated every hour. It is well known at the beginning of the day which hours of the day regulation power will be needed.

UC2.4 EV charger flexibility through user awareness

EV chargers' consumption usually can be shifted over time. The only requirement is that, at the end of the charging period, the battery must be at a determined state of charge. Therefore, it is an asset that can provide a large amount of flexibility. However, due to manufacturer software barriers, most of the EV chargers cannot be remotely controlled for this purpose.

Due to these conditions, the way to activate or deactivate these flexibility charges is through user interaction. Some indications, like traffic lights, are going to be installed together with explanatory panels to inform users, with the aim of increasing the local energy consumption usage.

This UC is intended to be installed in the sports centre Illa Esportiva EV charging station.

IV.2.6. Implementation Plan and Current State of Implementation

Here is an excerpt from the implementation plan until beginning of February; the full implementation plan can be found in the appendix.

Figure 27: AMB implementation plan timeline

Current State of Implementation

Regarding building III (“Montcada”, MB in the implementation plan), in general, the pilot is in sync with the original plan. Data were available from the very beginning, and based on these data, a DT has been built, and the system status has been predicted. Optimisation algorithms, however, have not yet been implemented.

In accordance with plans, for building I (“Castellbisbal Sports Centre”, IEB in the implementation plan), the necessary hardware has been purchased and is currently being installed. Delayed are the definition of the user interaction tool in building I. Data collection in building II (“Centre Cívic Virginia Amposta”, CCB in the implementation plan) has encountered unexpected issues. The building is connected to the internal municipal network, which has many connection restrictions due to its lack of a zero-thrust architecture. CIMNE and AMB are working with the municipality to find a secure enough solution that does not compromise the entire network. Also, market interaction has not been fully established yet.

IV.2.7. Pilot Specific KPIs

Table 12: Pilot specific KPIs: AMB

ID	Name	Formula	Temporal Granularity
AMB 1	Intraday benefit	$\frac{\sum_{t=0}^T (p_t^{intraday} E_t^{consumed}) - \sum_{t=0}^T (p_t^{day-ahead} E_t^{consumed})}{\sum_{t=0}^T (p_t^{day-ahead} E_t^{consumed})}$	Daily? Monthly? Idea of evaluating the gains of working with the intraday pricing not only day ahead. Basically, see what gains can be obtained from the combination of different markets.
AMB 2	Time displacement triggered	ΔT	By event (hours) Needed for capacity market, how much time I can displace consumption
AMB 3	Activation lag	$\Delta t_{\uparrow\downarrow\max}(\Delta P)$	By event Amount of time from trigger signal to max power reaction (up and down)
AMB 4	Rebound period	$\Delta T_{rebound}$	By event Duration of rebound effect (the amount of time needed to compensate the energy shift)

- Event and meeting rooms designed for networking and knowledge-sharing.

To further reduce its environmental impact, the building includes solar panels and green mobility facilities such as bicycle parking and EV charging stations.

Figure 29: Tour & Taxis aerial view

IV.3.1.b. Local Context

Tour & Taxis (Gare Maritime)

Figure 30: Gare Maritime

Gare Maritime, located within the Tour & Taxis district in Brussels, is a historic railway freight station that has been transformed into a sustainable, mixed-use urban hub. Originally built in the early 20th century, it was once one of Europe's largest freight train stations. Today, it stands as an example of adaptive reuse, combining historic architecture with modern sustainability principles.

Nextensa, one of the most renowned real estate developer in Belgium, created the project and initiated the construction of the residential area next to the Gare Maritime building. As only half of the solar production is consumed within the building, a part of the surplus is being shared to the residents of the site through an energy community. This allows the residents to reduce their invoices and have some savings.

The solar panels on the roof of the Greenbizz building are feeding energy to the common areas, the elevators, the offices and recently a battery. The surplus of the production is injected into the grid and sold to a supplier.

Greenbizz hosts a range of workshops where sustainable companies working on shared cars, sustainable food, diaper recycling and more. Those workshops have their own individual smart meters who are not linked to the solar panels and therefore do not benefit from its renewable production.

With the energy sharing project started by WeSmart in 2021, which is the first energy sharing project in Brussels, those workshops are since able to get a part of their consumption from the energy surplus of Greenbizz. This has helped them reduce their energy invoice and helped them think smarter about their consumption.

IV.3.1.c. Current SRI

SRI enhancement is planned via:

- Integration of energy optimization solutions with multi-energy approach (heat and electricity)
- Implementation of building-integrated flexibility services
- Deployment of energy community management and engagement tools
- Integration with DSO Sibelga for grid integration capabilities in real-time with dongles

Table 13: WeSmart SRI overview

Pilot Site	Initial SRI (start of BlueBird)	Current SRI (July 2025)	Target
Tour & Taxis	15%	38%	60%
Greenbizz.energy	18%	38%	60%

Original EU SRI version at M5 in the project

Figure 31: WeSmart T& BlueBird SRI score card at M5

IV.3.1.d. Stakeholder Overview

- Customers: About 40 for Tour&Taxis (T&T) and 10 for greenbizz
- Operational actors: WeSmart (service provider), Nextensa (owner of the T&T assets), Greenbizz (owner of the Greenbizz assets), Octave (provider of the battery)
- Electricity Actor: Sibelga (Brussels DSO)
- Regulatory Actor: Bruegel (Brussels energy regulator)

IV.3.1.e. Legal Framework

Launching a commercial energy community in Belgium, particularly in the Brussels-Capital Region, requires compliance with both EU and regional regulations. The EU Clean Energy Package (Directive (EU) 2019/944 and Directive (EU) 2018/2001) provides the foundation by recognizing *Citizen Energy Communities* and *Renewable Energy Communities*, granting them rights to generate, consume, store, and sell renewable energy.

In Brussels, the regional implementation is overseen by **Brugel**, the energy regulator, and facilitated technically by **Sibelga**, the local Distribution System Operator (DSO). Sibelga provides detailed guidance on energy sharing mechanisms, smart metering, and grid connection procedures ([Sibelga Energy Communities Guide](#)). Legal entities must adopt a transparent, open governance model and comply with grid access and tariff structures established by Brugel ([Brugel Energy Communities Overview](#)). Commercial energy communities must also ensure their structure aligns with the legal forms permitted under Belgian law, such as cooperatives or associations, and that all activities promote environmental and social benefits over profit maximization.

IV.3.2. Technical Infrastructure

IV.3.2.a. Electricity

IV.3.2.a.1. Physical Infrastructure:

For both buildings, the only source of production is from solar panels. There are 3 MWp installed on the roof of the Gare Maritime and 240 kWp on the roof of Greenbizz. Approximately a half of the production is consumed within the building for both sites. The rest is reinjected into the grid and can be shared virtually to the members of their respective energy communities.

For Tour & Taxis site, the members are located in a different building (Park Lane) than the one with the solar panels (Gare Maritime) whereas at Greenbizz the members are in the same building than the producer but with separate electric meters.

The Tour & Taxis configuration is as follows.

Figure 32: Power distribution Gare Maritime

At Greenbizz, a battery of 50 kW and 120 kWh is used to optimize the self-consumption of the building. This battery is owned by Octave (<https://octave.energy/en/>), which reuses batteries from electric vehicles.

Here is a diagram of the Greenbizz configuration:

Figure 33: Power distribution Greenbizz

IV.3.2.a.2. Energy mix for electricity

Community members currently use a combination of grid electricity and solar energy. At this time, there are no plans to incorporate other forms of renewable energy.

IV.3.2.a.3. What can be controlled?

Tour & Taxis

From a technical perspective, no direct control is currently possible at Tour & Taxis. The only available lever is consumer behavior. In this context, WeSmart can send behavioral recommendations to residents, but there are no systems in place that allow for active energy control.

Greenbizz

At Greenbizz, technical control is feasible due to the presence of a battery. However, the battery—provided by Octave—is currently being controlled by their own systems to optimize the building's self-consumption.

There is potential to discuss with the CEO of Greenbizz whether the battery control strategy could be adapted to better serve the goals of the energy community. While Bluebird members would still not have direct control, it may be possible to share data with Octave to enable a different control approach aligned with community needs.

IV.3.2.a.4. Data availability

Table 14: Data availability Tour & Taxi

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Electricity consumption from the members of the community of Tour&Taxis (kWh)	15 min	Gare Maritime building and Park Lane buildings	Historic (validated data available every month for the previous month)	Sibelga (Brussels DSO)
Electricity consumption from the members of the community of Greenbizz (kWh)	15 min	Greenbizz	1. Historic (validated data available every month for the previous month) 2. Day + 1 (non validated data available the day after the consumption)	Sibelga (Brussels DSO)
Greenbizz Battery State of Charge (kWh)	15 min	Greenbizz	Historic and real time	Octave.energy
Greenbizz Battery Power flows (kW)	15 min	Greenbizz	Historic and real time	Octave.energy

The monitoring of energy consumption, injection, and shared energy within both communities is already integrated into the WeSmart App. Users have access to clear and user-friendly visualizations that provide insights into the energy flows of their community. The data presented in the app is based on validated historical information, which is retrieved from the Distribution System Operator (DSO) portal. This data becomes available approximately one month after the actual measurements are taken, ensuring accuracy and reliability.

Below is an example of how this data is visualized for the Greenbizz project, illustrating how members can track their energy usage and understand the dynamics of energy sharing within the community:

Figure 34: WeSmart Dashboard

What still needs to be integrated to the app are the D+1 data for Greenbizz and the battery flows of Greenbizz.

IV.3.3. Social Infrastructure

IV.3.3.a. Stakeholders' Goals, Drivers, and Barriers

IV.3.3.a.1. Customers:

Goals:

The 40 customers at Tour & Taxis and 10 at Greenbizz aim to maintain their desired level of comfort while minimizing CO₂ emissions and reducing their energy expenses. They expect a reliable energy supply that supports their quality of life while benefiting from cost savings through optimized energy consumption.

Drivers:

The potential for energy flexibility optimization can lead to lower overall consumption and reduced energy bills. These 50 customers may also be motivated by sustainability goals and the opportunity to participate in an innovative energy model that encourages decarbonization.

Barriers:

The Tour & Taxis and Greenbizz customers require assurance that engaging in flexibility efforts will not compromise their comfort levels. Financial or service-based rewards must be sufficient to justify their involvement in adapting consumption habits. Additionally, a lack of familiarity with flexibility markets or energy management tools could hinder their engagement.

IV.3.3.a.2. Operational actors:

Goals:

WeSmart as the service provider, along with asset owners Nextensa (T&T) and Greenbizz, aim to optimize energy production and distribution while maintaining a robust and efficient system. Their goal is to balance cost-effectiveness with operational simplicity, ensuring reliable energy supply for customers. Octave, as the battery provider, focuses on maximizing storage efficiency and performance.

Drivers:

Reducing operational costs enhances overall competitiveness and decreases CO₂ emissions. The integration of Octave's battery storage system and participation in flexibility markets contribute to greater efficiency and sustainability.

Barriers:

Coordination between multiple operational actors (WeSmart, Nextensa, Greenbizz, and Octave) may create additional complexities that need careful management. Ensuring alignment between different stakeholders' interests and adopting optimal operational practices requires strategic planning.

IV.3.3.a.3. Electricity actor (Sibelga):

Goals:

Sibelga, as Brussels' DSO, aims to encourage flexible energy consumption patterns that align with grid needs. By shifting demand during periods of excess supply, they can enhance grid stability and efficiency in the Brussels region.

Drivers:

Flexible consumption enables Sibelga to optimize grid management and integrate renewable energy sources without overloading the system, particularly in the Tour & Taxis and Greenbizz areas.

Barriers:

- Coordination between multiple operational actors (WeSmart, Nextensa, Greenbizz, and Octave) may create additional complexities that need careful management. Ensuring alignment between different stakeholders' interests and adopting optimal operational practices requires strategic planning.
- The presence of battery storage and potential future PV generation may reduce reliance on grid electricity, which could affect Sibelga's grid management strategy. Managing energy flows and forecasting demand becomes more complex with these additional components.

IV.3.3.a.4. Regulatory actor:

Goals:

Brugel, as Brussels' energy regulator, aims for WeSmart to develop a scalable and efficient business model that reduces CO₂ emissions and increases flexibility, supporting the clean energy transition in the Brussels region.

Drivers:

A successful business case would help Brugel refine policies and evolve energy regulations to support innovative energy models in Brussels. Demonstrating the feasibility of energy flexibility and decentralized systems can shape future regulatory frameworks that encourage clean energy adoption.

Barriers:

Brugel must ensure consumer protection in new energy models, including fair pricing, transparent contracts, and reliable service. Balancing innovation with these protections is a key challenge in evolving regulations within the Brussels context.

IV.3.3.b. Current Stakeholder Communication Setup

The energy communities are coordinated through an Energy Community Manager. WeSmart maintains direct communication with all participants as well as with the Community Manager to ensure smooth operations and engagement.

At Greenbizz, decisions regarding new investments and possibly the steering of the battery for the energy community are made in consultation with the CEO of Greenbizz.

At Tour & Taxis, Nextensa is responsible for communicating with all residents about new investments and available services.

IV.3.3.c. Current Social Fabric

At Tour & Taxis, the energy community is composed primarily of residential participants. The shared renewable energy source for this community is a large solar installation located on the roof of the Gare Maritime building. This photovoltaic system generates the electricity that is partially redistributed among the residents through the energy sharing mechanisms in place.

In contrast, at Greenbizz, the energy community is made up of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating within the building. These business members participate in the community by consuming and, where applicable, contributing to the shared energy resources. The context and needs of the Greenbizz community are therefore more business-oriented, and the energy usage patterns reflect the operational requirements of the participating SMEs.

IV.3.4. Vision

Tour & Taxis

The Tour & Taxis energy community aims to showcase the economic, environmental, and social benefits of a decentralized energy system in a mixed-use urban environment. By integrating solar energy production, energy-efficient buildings, and smart consumption strategies, the community seeks to reduce CO₂ emissions, lower energy costs, and increase resident awareness of their energy use. This project not only emphasizes the importance of sustainable energy practices but also fosters a sense of collective responsibility and participation among residents.

Greenbizz

The Greenbizz energy community aspires to lead the way in sustainable energy management for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). By combining renewable energy sources, energy-efficient infrastructure, and advanced energy management systems, the community will reduce energy costs, lower carbon emissions, and optimize energy consumption among businesses. The project is designed to empower SMEs with the tools and knowledge necessary to reduce their environmental impact while promoting economic growth.

Through the implementation of flexible energy solutions and smart grid technology, the Greenbizz community will not only improve energy efficiency but also enhance the integration of renewable energy into the local business ecosystem. The project aims to create a replicable and scalable model that demonstrates how SMEs can actively participate in the energy transition, contributing to both the stability and sustainability of the grid while driving innovation in energy use within the commercial sector.

IV.3.4.a. Technical Building Flexibility

Tour & Taxis

Technical flexibility is not possible. Energy flexibility could be managed through behavioral recommendations, but there is no system to actively control or adjust energy use in real time.

Greenbizz

Technical flexibility could be achieved through the battery, which has the potential to optimize energy storage and consumption. However, this possibility is not yet a reality, as the battery is currently controlled by Octave for self-consumption optimization. Discussions are ongoing to explore how its management could be adjusted to better support the community's energy goals.

IV.3.4.b. Social Building Flexibility

Tour & Taxis and Greenbizz

Through the adoption of behavioral recommendations and energy-sharing mechanisms, the Tour & Taxis and Greenbizz communities will contribute to the creation of a more resilient and energy-efficient urban neighbourhood. The initiatives strive to establish a scalable model for integrating renewable energy into residential settings, ensuring that all residents play an active role in the energy transition while benefiting from cleaner, more affordable energy.

IV.3.4.c. Technical Infrastructure

Tour & Taxis

The technical infrastructure at **Tour & Taxis** is primarily focused on solar energy production and consumption management. A large photovoltaic system installed on the roof of the Gare Maritime building generates renewable energy for the community. However, the community does not have advanced energy management systems that allow for direct control or adjustment of energy use in real time. Instead, the focus is on encouraging residents to adapt their energy consumption through behavioral recommendations. These recommendations are based on data provided via the WeSmart App, which helps residents optimize their energy usage in alignment with the available solar power.

GreenBizz

Greenbizz utilizes a solar roof for renewable energy generation, paired with a battery for energy storage and management. The battery optimizes self-consumption within the building but is currently managed by a system that prioritizes building needs. There is potential for future flexibility in how the battery is controlled to better align with the energy community's goals.

IV.3.4.d. Social Infrastructure

Tour & Taxis

The social infrastructure at Tour & Taxis is managed via the WeSmart app. Communication and engagement are managed through Nextensa more generally on new investments, services and initiatives; and WeSmart on the energy community.

Greenbizz

The community consists of SMEs that collaborate on energy sharing. Communication is managed through the WeSmart App, where businesses receive data and recommendations to optimize energy use.

IV.3.5. Use Cases

Figure 35: UC Overview: WeSmart

UC 3.1 Residential consumption prediction and Charging Station considering battery and PV

Be able to predict the residential consumption from "Tour and Taxis" together with the forecasted PV production.

For the Greenbizz demo site predict electric consumption from the businesses together with PV production battery usage and EV Charging Stations.

UC 3.2 Optimize and generate actuating information

Use the Digital Twin to optimise the system operation by costs.

Operation for next day - next 24h - send alerts when something is wrong (alerted when PV is not producing what it should).

UC 3.3 Improve interaction with user

Gather data from the optimisation in order to send recommendations to the user. There are a web user interface and an APP from which the recommendations are going to be sent to the users. (residential + Greenbizz). Then select which data and in which frequency to communicate to the user, building on currently available communication means. Include different types of incentives: financial, motivational (see UC 3.5).

UC 3.4 Integrate and test Interconnect DSO interface

Test the Interconnect DSO Interface for real-time data acquisition at the T&T site Greenbizz. TSO is the entity controlling the flexibility market (not truly deploy, just testing). Scope: test the DSO interface in order to be prepared to interact with the DSO market.

UC 3.5 Analyse bills and financial incentives

Economic viability – The aim is to demonstrate the tangible reduced energy bills for end-users and incentivize increased REN production by (i) offering a preferential tariff to energy sharing participants

(produces and consumers) and (ii) enabling cost-effective energy consumption practices through DR tools available through the BlueBird controller and the WeSmart EMS.

Currently, the bill is used as a means of communication - propose recommendations how people can reduce their cost; the basis being that the price of shared energy in the community is lower than from price from the grid.

The idea is to generate monthly reports where people can see how their behaviour impacted their energy bill. Therefore, this UC should run only once a month.

IV.3.6. Implementation Plan and Current State of Implementation

Here is an excerpt from the implementation plan until beginning of February 2026; the full implementation plan can be found in the appendix.

Figure 36: WeSmart implementation plan timeline

Current State of Implementation

For a socio-technical experiment drafted in fall 2025, a first set of participants has been identified, however, it has not been finalized. The deployment of dongles is a little delayed, but meanwhile it has turned out that a direct connection with the DSO for data collection has been enabled and have been made accessible as of end of January. As the "testing" task includes testing not only of data collection but also of the algorithms and reaction from user communication, this is quite delayed, as without data, contrary to the implementation plan, there is no algorithm that can be tested beyond a very rough sketch from summer 2025. This means also no user recommendations could be generated, therefore, also these could not been tested in time.

As experimental setup takes long, there is the risk to lose the support of the already sourced participants.

IV.3.7. Pilot Specific KPIs

Table 15: Pilot specific KPIs of WeSmart

ID	Name	Formula	Temporal Granularity
WeSmart 1	Community Self-Consumption Rate	$SCR = (E_{\text{shared}} / E_{\text{produced}}) \times 100 \text{ [%]}$ <p>E_{shared}: = energy that is produced and consumed within the energy community during the same time interval (typically 15-minute periods). It represents the portion of local production that is directly matched with local consumption among community participants – i.e., the "collective self-consumption" as defined in Belgian regulation.</p> <p>E_{produced}: This is the total energy produced by the PV installations that are registered as part of the energy community (i.e., owned or contractually allocated to the community).</p>	Monthly
WeSmart 2	Participant Engagement Flexibility	$PEF = (\#participants_{\text{responding}} / \#participants_{\text{total}}) \times 100 \text{ [%]}$	By event / Monthly
WeSmart 3	Grid Dependency Reduction	$GDR = (E_{\text{grid_baseline}} - E_{\text{grid_optimized}}) / E_{\text{grid_baseline}} \times 100 \text{ [%]}$	Monthly / Yearly

IV.4. ENEA Operator: Office Building

IV.4.1. General Business Case Information

IV.4.1.a. Buildings and Local Context

IV.4.1.a.1. Buildings: Type and features

Enea Operator is one of the largest distribution system operators in Poland, operating in an area covering six provinces: Wielkopolska, West Pomerania, Kuyavian-Pomeranian, Lubuskie, and a small part of the Lower Silesian and Pomeranian provinces. The Enea Operator operating area is divided into five Distribution Branches: Bydgoszcz, Gorzów Wielkopolski, Poznań, Szczecin and Zielona Góra. In addition, the company operates in the area of 353 municipalities.

In addition, 31 Distribution Regions and 114 power stations operate within 5 Distribution Branches. Annually, Enea Operator supplies over 20 TWh of electricity to over 2,7 million customers in an area of 58.000 km².

The company's power infrastructure is:

- over 109.000 km of power lines (calculated per track), including almost 5,5 thousand km of 110 kV high-voltage lines.
- over 39 thousand transformer-distribution stations, including 255 HV/MV stations.

Enea Operator employs over 4.500 people.

The company is part of the Enea Capital Group. The company's headquarters is located in Poznań, at ul. Strzeszyńska 58, where the buildings of other companies that are part of the capital group are also located.

One of the buildings in the park belonging to the capital group is building B - this is a facility where some of the company's employees are located, who are employees of departments and offices reporting directly to the company's Management Board. The facility is powered by system heat from the heating network.

Figure 37: Enea Operator – Office Building – Poznań Strzeszyńska 58, building B

Technical parameters of the building:

- Building area: 851,54 m²
- Cubage: 10.466 m³
- Height: 11,95 m
- Usable area: 2.183 m²

The following installations were used in the building: water and sewage, hot water, rainwater, central heating, mechanical ventilation, lighting, electrical sockets, lightning protection and direct current elements.

IV.4.1.a.2. Local Context

Before serving its current function, the building underwent modernization (installation of air conditioning, floor renovation, new doors and door frames) - previously the facility was used by the energy emergency services and service workers.

IV.4.1.b. Current SRI

SRI EU original version in Proposal: 11,2% → 42,8%

SRI BlueBird Version at M5 in the project: 4,9%

Figure 38: ENEA office building BlueBird SRI score card at M5

IV.4.1.c. Stakeholder Overview

The main stakeholders involved in the Enea Operator Office Building demonstration within the BlueBird project include Enea Operator employees from Departments and Offices under the Management Board of the company.

These include, among others, employees of the Network Asset Management Department, employees of the Metering Information Management Department, employees of the Human Resources Development Department, employees of the Transport and Electromobility Office, employees of the Internal Control Office, employees of the Innovative Initiatives Office, employees of the Strategy and Project Management Office, employees of the Non-Network Real Estate Office and others.

IV.4.1.d. Legal Framework

Enea Operator is one of the largest distribution system operators in Poland.

The obligations of individual distributors have been specified by the Energy Law. It indicates that the DSO is primarily responsible for tasks such as:

- running network traffic in the distribution network,
- operating, maintaining and repairing the distribution network,
- planning the development of the distribution network,
- ensuring the expansion of the distribution network,
- cooperating with other power system operators or
- energy companies to the extent specified in the Energy Law,

- managing the power of specific generating units connected to the distribution network,
- balancing the system and managing system constraints;
- providing information to network users and operators of other power systems specified in the Energy Law,
- enabling the implementation of electricity sales agreements by recipients connected to the network by fulfilling the conditions specified in the Energy Law,
- maintaining an appropriate level of security of the distribution network operation.

IV.4.2. Technical Infrastructure

IV.4.2.a. Heat

Building B at 58 Strzeszyńska Street in Poznań is currently supplied with district heating from the city heating network. Each room has a radiator with a thermostat. The building employs 144 people. There are 69 office rooms and 14 service rooms (kitchens and toilets). The current number of radiators equipped with standard thermostats with manual control is 133. The above numbers may change at any time due to the adaptation of some rooms to the work of office workers, as well as the ongoing systematic relocation of employees (change of work space or changes in the number of people in the rooms). In addition, air conditioning has been installed in some rooms in the building, which can be turned on and off using remote control, and which simultaneously serves as cooling and heating.

Figure 39: Currently used thermostats and Air conditioning system with control panel

Table 16: Heat data availability: ENEA-Operator

Data [Name] [Unit]	and Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Overall annual heat demand [kWh]	yearly aggregate	Building level	Annual, prior years available	heating bill
Heating setpoint [°C]			No historic data. The exact completion of the table will be	

			indicated after the completion of the purchasing procedures for infrastructure.	
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IV.4.2.b. Electricity

IV.4.2.b.1. Physical Infrastructure:

Building B at 58 Strzeszyńska Street in Poznań is powered from the distribution network from the MV/LV transformer station located in the Enea Capital Group park. The building does not have any facilities in the field of renewable electricity sources or any electric car charging point.

IV.4.2.b.2. Energy mix for electricity

Electricity consumption is based 100% on electricity supplied to the building via the distribution network.

IV.4.2.b.3. What can be controlled?

At the moment, the only controlled asset in the building is the management of the air conditioning by remotely turning the devices on and off by the building administrators. Those rooms where the air conditioning is located have dedicated control panels, which are managed by the people staying in the room.

IV.4.2.b.4. Data availability

Table 17: Electricity data availability: ENEA-Operator

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Total electricity consumption [kWh]	two-month aggregation	Building level	Annual, prior years available	electricity bill

IV.4.3. Social Infrastructure

IV.4.3.a. Stakeholders' Goals, Drivers, and Barriers

IV.4.3.a.1. Enea Operator (EOP)

Goals:

The aim of Enea Operator's participation in the project through the participation of the non-network infrastructure building (building B at 58 Strzeszyńska Street in Poznań) is to check the possibility of operation of the building automation system by controlling heating parameters through controlling intelligent thermostats and integration with the existing platform in terms of the air conditioning system (or enabling the collection of data from individual installed air conditioning devices).

The next step will be to check the flexibility of the building in practice - through superior and subordinate control (building administration, individual users). An important aspect of future savings will also be, among others, control of temperature levels in the range of working days and non-working days. So far, Enea Operator has not used BMS systems in non-network infrastructure buildings.

Drivers:

The main factor in the implementation of the project in this facility is to check the possibilities of managing the building's energy infrastructure in terms of heating, as well as to learn about the possibilities of operating BMS systems in practice. Additionally, we plan to check what financial savings will be possible to achieve.

Barriers:

Enea Operator is bound by public procurement law - the implementation of the task is burdened with time risk due to long-term procedures and proceedings.

The entire task - Delivery and installation of a building automation system (BMS) together with the implementation of heating device control in building B at ul. Strzeszyńska 58 in Poznań - will be implemented in one procedure.

IV.4.3.b. Current Stakeholder Communication Setup

As part of the BlueBird project, Enea Operator will closely cooperate with the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), which provides substantive support for Enea Operator in the implementation of BlueBird.

Building B at 58 Strzeszynska Street in Poznań is fully owned by Enea Operator.

IV.4.3.c. Current Social Fabric

Building B at 58 Strzeszynska Street in Poznań is fully owned by Enea Operator. It is not used for any other purpose than the professional activities of Enea Operator employees. It is equipped with standard office social rooms, such as kitchens.

IV.4.4. Vision

Building B at 58 Strzeszyńska Street in Poznań does not function as a critical infrastructure facility. Its integration with flexibility markets and the possibility of testing the operation of such functions is possible in the field of heat management.

The action is consistent with the vision of optimizing municipal assets in terms of demand-side flexibility, and thus reducing operating costs, increasing network stability and contributing to the local energy transformation.

IV.4.4.a. Technical Building Flexibility

The basic technical goal is to have a building automation system with reliable control options for both the building administration and office workers in an individual scope. The building automation system (BMS) should be an open system and scalable to the needs of the recipient. The platform should enable viewing, control - full management and visualization of measurement data from various types of devices. The basic role of the platform should be to integrate and merge data from thermostats enabling remote reading (for implementation and as part of this investment) and integration with the existing platform in the scope of the air conditioning system (or enable collection of data from individual installed air conditioning devices).

The basic functions of the BMS system, which would meet the tasks and goals of Enea Operator are:

- Visualization of measurement data from individual measurement devices in a user-friendly and intuitive form;
- Creation of dedicated measurement dashboards with selected data (temperature, energy savings) - taking into account dates, costs, energy consumption, a welcome indicator of CO₂ emission reduction;

- Possibility of uploading work schedules and estimating potential savings (% lower heat energy consumption);
- Advanced data analysis – comparing work scenarios: example – what energy savings will we achieve in a building if the thermostat work schedule is set to 20 degrees Celsius over a 24-hour period instead of 22 degrees Celsius;
- Possibility of integrating the building automation system (BMS) with other systems – a key issue in terms of implementing the BlueBird project (the system should enable issuing signals);

IV.4.4.b. Social Building Flexibility

The entities affected by the construction of the BMS system in the Enea Operator non-network building are: office workers, building management staff, IT network administrators (who will support the implementation process of the technical solution), the heating network (by changing the flow of thermal power to the building as variable instead of constant).

The system automatically adjusts office heating, raising or lowering temperature settings when possible, helping to save energy and promoting flexible energy use. Manual temperature adjustments via thermostats will still be possible, but the system works best when manual adjustments are kept to a minimum.

By centralizing data and leveraging intelligent algorithms, the BMS enables, among other things:

- real-time monitoring of energy and utility consumption,
- optimization of technical equipment operating parameters,
- reduction of energy costs through automation and intelligent operating scenarios,
- rapid detection of irregularities and support for maintenance activities.

The activities are aimed at improving not only economic efficiency (cost reduction), but also at raising awareness among Enea Operator employees about the importance of energy efficiency and the impact of individual units on the overall effect.

IV.4.4.c. Technical Infrastructure

The long-term goal is to create a repeatable and scalable infrastructure model, showing how municipal assets can evolve into flexibility centers. Enea Operator has a number of non-network infrastructure buildings - power stations or headquarters of the company's Distribution Districts and Distribution Divisions. The implementation of the project will allow for the establishment of further development and operation possibilities in terms of flexibility on other infrastructure facilities.

IV.4.4.d. Social Infrastructure

By presenting the effects of the project implementation and achieving the assumed goals, it will be easier for the Management Board of Enea Operator to make a decision on further modernization of the building infrastructure in terms of BMS systems and potential participation in the flexibility markets.

IV.4.5. Use Cases

BC #3 ENEA-Office

- UC 4.1** Predictive heating and monitoring
- UC 4.2** Heating control with the use of remote thermostats
- UC 4.3** Flexibility in heat consumption – a recommendation system to support user's decisions concerning thermostat settings in a predictive way to respect comfort constraints

Figure 40: BC Overview: ENEA-Office

UC 4.1 Predictive heating and monitoring

Predict the energy consumption from the heating system of the ENEA office building heated through district heating system. The aim is to use these predictions to optimise the heating system, therefore the model needs to incorporate the control variables (thermostat control).

UC 4.2 Heating control with the use of remote thermostats

Use the consumption modelling framework to optimise the heating of the building. This consumption is optimized for reducing the heating cost through actuating in the thermostats.

UC 4.3 Flexibility in heat consumption – a recommendation system to support user's decisions concerning thermostat settings in a predictive way to respect comfort constraints

Maximize the probability that user implement the recommendations.

IV.4.6. Implementation Plan and Current State of Implementation

Here is an excerpt from the implementation plan until beginning of February 2026; the full implementation plan can be found in the appendix.

Figure 41: ENEA-Operator Implementation plan timeline

Current state of Implementation

Tender procedure has been implemented in unison with the other ENEA pilot, the grid buildings. Both are part of a critical infrastructure, which requires an intense tender procedure (including network security requirements or creating documentation for the tender). These tasks have been accomplished in accordance with implementation planning. However, even considering that this is a complex process, signing of a contract took too long, so that hardware has not yet been supplied and installed. Without the hardware, data collection could not be set up as planned. This poses a risk, as there is only one winter left for the demo to implement heat-based experiments. However, for summer, to do testing of algorithms with the AC might still be possible.

All other preliminary tasks as building and configuring a BMS server have been implemented in due time.

IV.4.7. Pilot Specific KPIs

Table 18: Pilot Specific KPIs ENEA-Operator

ID	Name	Formula	Temporal Granularity
ENEA-Office 1	Cost purchase & installation of smart products vs savings (KPI 2.12)	Heat energy cost savings / (purchase cost + installation cost)	Annually

IV.5. PSNC & ENEA Operator: Grid Building

IV.5.1. General Business Case Information

IV.5.1.a. Buildings and Local Context

IV.5.1.a.1. Building 1: Type and features

Enea Operator is one of the largest distribution system operators in Poland, operating in an area covering six provinces: Wielkopolska, West Pomerania, Kuyavian-Pomeranian, Lubuskie, and a small part of the Lower Silesian and Pomeranian provinces. The Enea Operator operating area is divided into five Distribution Branches: Bydgoszcz, Gorzów Wielkopolski, Poznań, Szczecin and Zielona Góra. In addition, the company operates in the area of 353 municipalities.

In addition, 31 Distribution Regions and 114 power stations operate within 5 Distribution Branches. Annually, Enea Operator supplies over 20 TWh of electricity to over 2,7 million customers in an area of 58.000 km².

The company's power infrastructure is:

- over 109.000 km of power lines (calculated per track), including almost 5,5 thousand km of 110 kV high-voltage lines.
- over 39 thousand transformer-distribution stations, including 255 HV/MV stations.

Enea Operator employs over 4.500 people.

As part of the BlueBird project, the management of the temperature of the facility in the switchboard and control room will be tested. At the stage of creating the project application, a decision was made to select the Kuczyna power station, located in the Greater Poland province in the Gostyń district.

Figure 42: Enea Operator – HV/MV power station Kuczyna

Characteristics of the Kuczyna power station: the facility transforms the voltage from 110 kV to 15 kV (two transformers with a capacity of 16 MVA each), a 110 kV overhead, single-system, two-section switchboard with SF6 gas circuit breakers. The station has six entrances from the outside: to the compensation unit no. 1 and 2, to the rooms with compensation batteries no. 1 and 2, to the 15 kV switchboard and the main entrance to the communication room, which is also connected to the battery room, communication room, control room and toilet. An additional connection is the passage between the control room and the 15 kV switchboard.

IV.5.1.a.2. Local Context

Each of the power stations is different from each other - they are not all the same buildings - the differences result primarily from the construction of the 15 kV switchgear - depending on the number of outgoing fields of the medium voltage line, there can be from a dozen to about 80 of them. HV/MV power station Kuczyna is characterized by a small number of outflow fields and relatively low power that is subject to transformation from 110 to 15 kV, which is why this facility is very suitable for pilot tests.

The station is a maintenance-free facility (without constant on-site service) - the facility is visited by energy emergency service employees when planned work is to be carried out on the facility (equipment inspections, checks). Most devices are operated using telemechanics by dispatchers responsible for monitoring the devices and their correct operation, as well as their remote operation.

The basic problem in terms of the building's energy efficiency is that all devices responsible for temperature aspects in the building are set to fixed values and controlled - both the air conditioning and the heating using electric stone radiators - to the point where both devices operate simultaneously.

IV.5.1.b. Current SRI

SRI in Proposal: 2,3% → 36,6%

*SRI BlueBird Version at M5: **3,1%***

Figure 43: ENEA grid building BlueBird SRI score card at M5

IV.5.1.c. Stakeholder Overview

Kuczyna HV/MV power station is a strictly guarded facility - access to it for unauthorized persons is prohibited. Access to the facility is available to selected employees of the energy emergency service after undergoing dedicated training in the operation of station devices and to employees of Enea Serwis (companies responsible for device inspections).

IV.5.1.d. Legal Framework

Enea Operator is one of the largest distribution system operators in Poland.

The obligations of individual distributors have been specified by the Energy Law. It indicates that the DSO is primarily responsible for tasks such as:

- running network traffic in the distribution network,
- operating, maintaining and repairing the distribution network,
- planning the development of the distribution network,
- ensuring the expansion of the distribution network,
- cooperating with other power system operators or energy companies to the extent specified in the Energy Law,
- managing the power of specific generating units connected to the distribution network,

- balancing the system and managing system constraints;
- providing information to network users and operators of other power systems specified in the Energy Law,
- enabling the implementation of electricity sales agreements by recipients connected to the network by fulfilling the conditions specified in the Energy Law,
- maintaining an appropriate level of security of the distribution network operation.

IV.5.2. Technical Infrastructure

IV.5.2.a. Heat

The basic aspect of operation in a facility is the cooling and heating devices responsible for maintaining a constant temperature in the facility.

The task of the air cooling system is to separate the total heat gains in the rooms: Control Room, Communication Room, Battery Room and Switchboard by using SPLIT system air conditioners operating on circulating air, e.g., LG Electronics. Additionally, during the heating period, the devices operate in heating mode. The facility has designed independent SPLIT systems with wall-mounted internal units. The devices are connected to external units with refrigerant pipes. The power supply of the internal units (which are mounted about 30 cm from the ceiling) is independent of the external unit, while communication with the external unit takes place via control cables. The operation of the devices is regulated by a remote control - a wireless controller. Through inverter control of the external unit fan motor, the system ensures low noise level, effective and fast heating, cooling and minimal electricity consumption.

Figure 44: Cooling/heating system ceiling unit

The basis for all considerations on central heating installation solutions is the heat balance. Data from architectural and construction bases were used to determine the total demand for covering heat losses in the analysed rooms by building partitions and ventilation. Based on the balance, heating elements for individual rooms were adopted.

The facility is heated by air heating (air conditioning and electric heating).

In the Battery Room, Control Room, Switchboard Room, Communication Room and Toilet, Termar stone radiators were designed. Radiator construction: stone plate, resistance heating element with power depending on the size of the radiator (300-2000W), TE-4 standard or TE-4 CZZ radiator temperature sensor (battery room) and BOT-1 temperature limiter, power cord, Decorative screws securing the radiator to the hangers

Radiator hangers, Radiator screen - standard glued to the wall or insulation board mounted on the back wall of the radiator.

Figure 45: HV/MV power station Kuczyna - Heating scheme

The diagram above shows the following devices:

- Electric radiator with stone plate.
- TE-4K temperature controller.
- TE-4KCZZ temperature controller with external temperature sensor.
- BOT-1 heating plate temperature limiter.
- External temperature sensor.
- Temperature drop signal sensor.

Table 19: List of air conditioning devices ENEA

Model name	Number of pieces	Description
D09CM.NSJ	1	Indoor unit - ceiling
D18CM.NSK	5	Indoor unit - ceiling
D09CM.UL2	1	Outdoor unit Cooling capacity 2,5 kW
D18CM.UL2	5	Outdoor unit Cooling capacity 5 kW

Control is currently via a dedicated remote control.

Table 20: List of heating installation devices

Model name / Power	Number of pieces	Description
600 W	1	Termar electric thermal heater
1300 W	1	Termar electric thermal heater
1700 W	4	Termar electric thermal heater
1800 W	1	Termar electric thermal heater
2000 W	3	Termar electric thermal heater

Figure 46: Termar electric thermal heater and Temperature controller (heat)

Currently, the basic problem at power stations is the lack of knowledge about the costs of maintaining constant temperature and the related bills. The power station is supplied with cooling using devices for its own needs - at the level of 15 kV, a transformation to the level of 400 V takes place using a compensation unit, thus supplying electricity to all necessary devices on the facility, but also control devices outside the facility (110 kV switchboard), hence there is no distinction between the costs of operating the power station separately for costs related to heating and cooling.

Table 21: Planned data

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Heating power [kW]			No historic data. The exact completion of the table will be indicated after the completion of the purchasing procedures for infrastructure	
Cooling power [kW]				
Heating setpoint [oC]				
Heating setpoint [oC]				
Internal temperature [oC]				

IV.5.3. Social Infrastructure

IV.5.3.a. Stakeholders' Goals, Drivers, and Barriers

IV.5.3.a.1. Enea Operator (EOP)

Goals:

The aim of the activity within the project is to increase the energy awareness of Enea Operator employees, including energy emergency service employees, and to attempt to economically manage the costs of cooling and heating in buildings.

Drivers:

The main goal and motivating factor for action is to verify potential economic savings and to assess the possibilities of effective management of the building's heating and cooling equipment.

Barriers:

Enea Operator is bound by public procurement law - the implementation of the task is burdened with time risk due to long-term procedures and proceedings.

The main barrier is the criticality of the facility - the power station is always a key point for electricity recipients, who have energy supplied directly from this facility. All actions must be carried out with great care due to the energy security of Enea Operator's recipients and customers. In the event of a power outage for the facility, the energy emergency service is forced to perform a series of switches in the distribution network in order to ensure energy supplies to recipients. In addition, some key rooms - such as the battery room - require strict key technical requirements, which can only be subject to minimal changes.

IV.5.3.b. Current Stakeholder Communication Setup

As part of the BlueBird project, Enea Operator will closely cooperate with the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), which provides substantive support for Enea Operator in the implementation of BlueBird.

HV/MV power station Kuczyna is fully owned by Enea Operator.

IV.5.3.c. Current Social Fabric

HV/MV power station Kuczyna is fully owned by Enea Operator. It is not used for any other purpose than the professional activities of Enea Operator employees. The social rooms in the control room include a workstation (chair, table, telephone, documentation) and a toilet room.

IV.5.4. Vision

The aim of the BlueBird project at the Enea Operator power station is to check the possibilities of managing heating and cooling sources, as well as to check and verify the possibilities of improving the energy efficiency management of the switchboard and control room buildings. An additional aspect is that this is critical infrastructure, hence these activities should be performed with appropriate caution and verification - the rooms include, among others, a battery room, which is responsible for backup power supply in the event of a voltage failure at the station.

The final effect for Enea Operator will be the integration of the BMS building automation management system also with the building and the goals implemented within Business Case 4.

Ultimately, as part of the project, a pilot heating and cooling management system will be built, which would be easy to scale to other Enea Operator power facilities. The task within BC5 will be carried out jointly with the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC).

IV.5.4.a. Technical Building Flexibility

The basic technical task is to build a concept for a scalable energy efficiency management system in HV/MV power stations, of which Enea Operator owns over 255. The project will involve testing a cooling and heating management solution by experts from Enea Operator and the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC). Checking and testing the possibilities of managing energy efficiency and flexibility is aimed at verifying the hypothesis about the possibility of obtaining high efficiency results in the context of temperature management at the facility - as part of the project, the possibilities of reducing temperatures will be checked.

IV.5.4.b. Technical Infrastructure

The long-term goal is to create a repeatable and scalable infrastructure model, showing how municipal assets can evolve into flexibility centers. Enea Operator has a number of non-network infrastructure buildings - power stations or headquarters of the company's Distribution Districts and Distribution Divisions. The implementation of the project will allow for the establishment of further development and operation possibilities in terms of flexibility on other infrastructure facilities.

IV.5.4.c. Social Infrastructure

By presenting the effects of the project implementation and achieving the assumed goals, it will be easier for the Management Board of Enea Operator to make a decision on further modernization of the building infrastructure in terms of BMS systems and potential participation in the capacity market (e.g., through DSR services).

IV.5.5. Use Cases

Figure 47: BC Overview: ENEA-Grid

UC 5.1 Simple non-intrusive building electric heating and cooling monitoring and Prediction

Create the modelling framework for the ENEA grid building energy consumption. This modelling framework will be based on the collection of the required data and will be used to predict the electric consumption for

heating and cooling of the building. This model will be centered on the heating and cooling consumption as will be the base to actuate in the building.

UC 5.2 Optimize to generate actuations A) heating: generate target temperatures for thermostats, B) cooling: generate on/off patterns for Acs

Use the consumption modelling framework to optimise the cooling and heating of the building. This consumption is optimized for reducing the climatization cost.

UC 5.3 Demonstrate the use of a dynamic heating & cooling management as a preparation for TSO interaction

Determine the flexibility capabilities with the aim of aggregating the energy flexibility of many buildings and sell this flex to the TSO and implement an impact and benefit analysis.

IV.5.6. Implementation Plan and Current State of Implementation

Here is an excerpt from the implementation plan until beginning of February 2026; the full implementation plan can be found in the appendix.

Figure 48: ENEA-Grid implementation plan timeline

Current state of Implementation

Tender procedure has been implemented in unison with the other ENEA pilot, the office building. Both are part of a critical infrastructure, which requires an intense tender procedure (including network security requirements or creating documentation for the tender). These tasks have been accomplished in accordance with implementation planning. However, even considering that this is a complex process, signing of a contract took too long, so that hardware has not yet been supplied and installed. Without the hardware, data collection could not be set up as planned. This poses a risk, as there is only one winter left

for the demo to implement heat-based experiments. However, for summer, to do testing of algorithms with the AC might still be possible.

All other preliminary tasks as building and configuring a BMS server have been implemented in due time.

IV.5.7. Pilot Specific KPIs

Table 22: Pilot Specific KPIs ENEA-Grid

ID	Name	Formula	Temporal Granularity
ENEA-Grid 1	Simulated market revenues from flexibility provision on the capacity market	Simulated sum of revenues generated from flexibility on the capacity market participation	Annually

IV.6. ENK: Waterworks building with renewable storage

IV.6.1. General Business Case Information

IV.6.1.a. Buildings and Local Context

IV.6.1.a.1. Building 1: Type and features

The **Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB)** is legally constituted as a water association under the Austrian Water Rights Act (Wasserrechtsgesetz). Its headquarters are located at *Beim Wasserwerk 3, 7400 Oberwart, Austria*. The association is responsible for supplying drinking, utility, and firefighting water to approximately 50.000 residents across 30 municipalities in the Oberwart district and parts of the Güssing district. The WVSB operates under the management of Ing. Christian Portschy, who serves as the managing director. The WVSB is the owner and operator of the Waterworks Oberwart.

The **Waterworks Oberwart** serves as the central hub for the Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB), ensuring the provision of drinking, utility, and firefighting water to approximately 50.000 residents across 30 municipalities. Originally established in 1962, the facility has continuously evolved to meet the region's growing water demands. A significant modernization took place in 1996, updating the infrastructure to accommodate an expanding service area and increasing population. As part of this redevelopment, new office spaces were added to support the administrative functions of the association.

The current waterworks facility was constructed in 1995 following an architectural competition won by Ing. Hansjörg Weinhandl. Designed to meet both present and future water demands, the facility has a total capacity of 100 liters per second, equating to 8.64 million liters per day. To enhance operational efficiency, the WVSB relocated its administrative offices in 2013 to a newly established municipal utility center adjacent to the waterworks. This move provided employees with a modern and spacious working environment while fostering synergies with other municipal services, ultimately improving overall service delivery.

The waterworks is equipped with advanced process control and monitoring systems, enabling real-time management of water extraction, treatment, and distribution. This ensures a reliable and efficient water supply for the region. The facility also integrates a 100 kWp photovoltaic system and a 300 kWh battery storage, contributing to its energy self-sufficiency and sustainability.

Architecturally, the building balances functionality with aesthetic appeal, reflecting its role as a key regional infrastructure asset. It houses both operational areas for water treatment and distribution as well as dedicated office spaces for administrative staff, ensuring an efficient and comfortable working environment for employees.

Figure 49: The Waterworks building

IV.6.1.a.2. Local Context

The Waterworks Oberwart is centrally located in the town of Oberwart, Burgenland, Austria, serving as the headquarters for the Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB). This facility is integral to the region's water infrastructure, ensuring the provision of drinking, utility, and firefighting water to approximately 50.000 residents across 30 municipalities.

In 2013, the WVSB relocated its administrative offices to a newly established municipal utility center adjacent to the waterworks. This strategic move provided staff with a modern and spacious working environment, fostering synergies with other municipal services and enhancing overall service delivery to the community.

The waterwork is connected to the regional power grid managed by **Netz Burgenland GmbH**, the primary distribution system operator (DSO) in the Burgenland region. **Netz Burgenland** is responsible for the reliable and efficient delivery of electricity and gas to households and businesses throughout the area.

The town of Oberwart has been proactive in implementing innovative energy solutions, exemplified by the **Loadshift Oberwart project** (2013 – 2017). This initiative aimed to develop and test an urban, cross-building energy management system for electricity, heating, and cooling. By integrating various energy producers and consumers, including facilities like the waterworks, the project sought to optimize load profiles and enhance the integration of renewable energy sources. The insights gained from this project have been instrumental in advancing energy efficiency and sustainability in the region.

Waterworks Oberwart is a critical component of the region's water supply infrastructure and also a participant in forward-thinking energy management practices, contributing to the sustainable development of Oberwart and its surrounding communities.

IV.6.1.b. Current SRI

The Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) assessment for the Waterworks Oberwart, as done during the proposal phase, provides an overview of the facility's technological and operational capabilities in terms of energy efficiency, flexibility, and digital integration. With a total SRI score of 7,3%, the assessment indicates that while some smart functionalities exist, there is considerable room for improvement in automation and energy management. The facility has implemented certain efficiency measures, particularly through its photovoltaic system and battery storage, but real-time energy optimization and automated control mechanisms remain limited.

The evaluation of energy flexibility and storage reflects the facility's current state, with a low score of 2,4%. Although a 300 kWh battery storage system is installed, its utilization for grid-interactive flexibility and automated demand response is not yet fully developed. Similarly, while the pumping operations allow for controlled energy use, they are not dynamically optimized for grid interaction. Comfort-related aspects score moderately at 8,3%, acknowledging that while environmental conditions within the facility are maintained at a functional level, no advanced automation for climate control is in place. Given that the waterworks is an industrial site rather than a residential or commercial space, comfort features play a secondary role.

The assessment of convenience, with a score of 18,4%, suggests that some degree of automation is already implemented in the facility's core operations. This includes process monitoring and system efficiency measures, particularly in water treatment and distribution. Maintenance and fault prediction, with a score of 8,7%, indicate that while real-time monitoring systems exist, there is still a reliance on manual oversight rather than predictive analytics for equipment management. Information provided to occupants scores at 10,3%, as operational data is available through monitoring systems, but more advanced real-time analytics or user feedback mechanisms are not in place.

The domain-specific assessments highlight particular strengths and weaknesses. Electricity readiness scores the highest at 35,3%, reflecting the presence of renewable energy generation, storage, and smart metering. Domestic hot water readiness is evaluated at 30,0%, while heating readiness stands at 16,7%, indicating that heating systems are in place but without extensive smart control capabilities. Other domains such as ventilation, lighting, and dynamic building envelope were not significant contributors to the overall readiness of the facility.

Figure 50: ENK SRI EU standard score card in the proposal

Figure 51: ENK BlueBird SRI score card at M5

The Waterworks Oberwart demonstrates a foundational level of smart grid readiness with integrated renewable energy and basic monitoring systems. However, the current level of automation, digital control, and energy flexibility remains relatively low, limiting the facility’s ability to fully interact with advanced grid management systems.

IV.6.1.c. Stakeholders

The main stakeholders involved in the Waterworks Oberwart demonstration within the BlueBird project include the following:

- **Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB)** – The owner and operator of the waterworks, responsible for water extraction, treatment, and distribution. The WVSB plays a central role in ensuring operational reliability and integrating new energy management solutions within its infrastructure.
- **WVSB Employees** – The operational staff responsible for the daily management and maintenance of the waterworks. Their role includes monitoring energy consumption, ensuring uninterrupted water supply, and integrating new digital tools for predictive load management and flexibility optimization.
- **Energie Kompass GmbH (ENK)** – The technology and flexibility aggregator responsible for implementing smart energy solutions, optimizing energy consumption, and integrating the waterworks into flexibility markets through advanced demand-side management strategies.
- **Energienetze Burgenland GmbH (DSO)** – The distribution system operator (DSO) responsible for managing the local electricity grid, ensuring a stable and efficient energy supply, and facilitating grid interactions for demand-side flexibility services.
- **Municipality of Oberwart** – The local government authority, overseeing regional infrastructure developments and supporting initiatives that enhance energy efficiency and sustainability in municipal services.
- **Citizens of the Oberwart Region** – The 50.000 residents across 30 municipalities who rely on the Waterworks Oberwart for a stable and high-quality supply of drinking, utility, and firefighting water. The reliability and efficiency of the facility directly impact the well-being of the local population, making them key beneficiaries of any improvements in water management and energy optimization.

IV.6.1.d. Legal Framework

The Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB) is a public-law association (Wasserverband) established under the Austrian Water Rights Act (Wasserrechtsgesetz, WRG 1959). In Austria, water associations (Wasserverbände) are legal entities of public law (juristische Personen des öffentlichen Rechts) that are responsible for the management, supply, and distribution of water across multiple municipalities.

WVSB operates as a non-profit entity, owned collectively by the municipalities it serves, and is tasked with ensuring a reliable and high-quality drinking water supply. As a public-law corporation, WVSB is subject to municipal oversight, Austrian water regulations, and financial auditing by public authorities, but it retains operational independence in managing infrastructure, service provision, and financial planning.

The legal framework governing the Waterworks Oberwart is shaped by Austrian and European regulations related to water management, energy efficiency, and grid integration. As a critical infrastructure for public water supply, the Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB) operates under the **Austrian Water Rights Act (Wasserrechtsgesetz, WRG 1959)**, which sets requirements for the extraction, treatment, and distribution of drinking water, ensuring compliance with quality standards and environmental protection measures. Additionally, the waterworks must adhere to the **Austrian Drinking Water Ordinance (Trinkwasserordnung)**, which establishes strict health and safety regulations for potable water supply.

From an energy perspective, the facility is subject to the **Renewables Development Act (Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetz, EAG 2021)**, which promotes decentralized renewable energy production and participation in energy communities. The **Electricity Industry and Organization Act (Elektrizitätswirtschafts- und -organisationsgesetz, EIWOG 2010)** governs the interaction with Energienetze Burgenland GmbH (the regional DSO), particularly regarding grid access, flexibility services, and demand-side management participation. The waterworks also falls under EU directives such as the **Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU, revised 2018/2002)** and the **Electricity Market Directive (EU 2019/944)**, which encourage demand-response participation, smart metering, and digitalization of energy systems. These regulations provide the legal foundation for the integration of smart grid technologies and energy flexibility services,

enabling the Waterworks Oberwart to explore new models of renewable energy utilization and grid-supportive operations.

As a public-law association, the Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB) is subject to Austrian **public procurement law (Vergaberecht)**, which governs the acquisition of goods and services by publicly controlled entities. This legal framework impacts WVSB's ability to participate in Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), as the procurement process for utilizing shared energy resources is currently unclear under existing regulations. Due to these legal constraints, WVSB has not yet joined a local REC, as participation would require compliance with procurement rules to ensure fair and transparent contracting. As of February 2025, legal experts are working to define the necessary procedures that would allow WVSB to integrate into an REC while adhering to public sector procurement requirements.

IV.6.2. Technical Infrastructure

IV.6.2.a. Electricity

IV.6.2.a.1. Physical Infrastructure:

The Waterworks Oberwart is connected to the low-voltage grid (grid level 6) operated by Energienetze Burgenland GmbH for its water treatment and distribution processes. The facility has an on-site photovoltaic (PV) system with a capacity of 100 kWp, which contributes to local electricity generation. Additionally, a 300 kWh battery storage system is installed to enhance self-consumption of renewable energy and provide limited backup power in case of grid instability.

No biomass or other renewable generation technologies are installed at the site. The electricity infrastructure primarily supports water pumping operations, administrative functions, and process automation systems. There is a connection to the DEMS system developed in the Loadshift Oberwart and Industry4Redispatch projects, that provides VPP functionality to integrate into demand-side management (DSM) and flexibility markets.

IV.6.2.a.2. Energy mix for electricity

The facility's electricity consumption is a combination of grid supply and on-site solar generation. The share of self-consumed renewable electricity depends on real-time PV production, the operational status of the waterworks, and the charging strategy of the battery storage system. The grid supply consists of the Austrian national energy mix, which is primarily based on hydropower, wind, and solar energy, supplemented by conventional power sources.

IV.6.2.a.3. What can be controlled?

The main controllable elements within the electricity infrastructure are:

- **Water Pumps:** Pumping operations can be optimized for load shifting and peak shaving, allowing flexible operation based on energy price signals or grid conditions.
- **Battery Storage:** The 300 kWh battery system can be charged and discharged strategically to maximize self-consumption, reduce peak demand, or participate in flexibility markets.
- **PV Generation Utilization:** The integration of photovoltaic energy into the system can be managed to prioritize self-consumption over grid export, depending on operational needs.
- **Grid Interaction:** Although no direct market participation is currently in place, the facility has the potential to interact with redispatch markets and demand-side response programs through a Virtual Power Plant (VPP) setup.

Some fixed loads, such as administrative office electricity use and process control systems, are not actively controllable within the energy management framework.

IV.6.2.a.4. Data availability

Table 23: Data availability ENK

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Total electricity consumption [kWh]	15' intervalls	Building level	Whole year, Historic data available	Customer portal of energy supplier
Actual electricity consumption / feed-in [kW]	1' intervals	Building level	Periods of VVP pilot operation historic data available	DEMS software API
PV generation [kWh] (partially)	15' intervalls	Inverter level (only 1 inverter is currently monitored)	Whole year, Historic data available	Inverter monitoring system
Automation System: Additional data is available in the operations automation system	Daily	System/asset level	Partial availability	Waterwork automatisisation system

IV.6.3. Social Infrastructure

IV.6.3.a. Stakeholders' Goals, Drivers, and Barriers

IV.6.3.a.1. Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB)

Goals:

WVSB aims to ensure a stable, high-quality, and cost-effective water supply for the 50.000 residents across its service area. As an operator of critical infrastructure, it seeks to enhance energy efficiency, reduce operational costs, and increase the resilience of its water supply system. The integration of renewable energy and flexibility measures is viewed as a way to mitigate electricity price volatility and contribute to sustainability goals.

Drivers:

The main drivers for WVSB include rising electricity costs, which directly impact operational expenses, and the need for energy security in water distribution. The presence of on-site PV generation and battery storage provides an opportunity to optimize energy use and increase self-consumption. Additionally, regulatory and societal pressure to increase sustainability encourages WVSB to explore smart energy solutions.

Barriers:

WVSB's public procurement obligations under Austrian law (Vergaberecht) limit its ability to directly participate in energy-sharing agreements such as a Renewable Energy Community (REC). The lack of clear regulatory pathways for public entities engaging in flexibility markets further complicates market

integration. Internally, organizational adaptation to digital energy solutions is a challenge, as the primary focus remains on water management rather than energy optimization.

IV.6.3.a.2. WWSB Employees

Goals:

WWSB employees aim to ensure the reliable operation of the waterworks while integrating new energy flexibility mechanisms in a way that does not compromise core water supply functions. Their primary objectives include maintaining operational stability, minimizing energy costs, and improving efficiency through digital solutions. Employees also seek to reduce manual workload by utilizing automated forecasting and scheduling tools.

Drivers:

The introduction of predictive load forecasting and automated flexibility management offers employees greater control and visibility over energy consumption without increasing complexity. The ability to optimize energy use while maintaining uninterrupted water supply is a key incentive. Additionally, training and upskilling in energy management and digital tools provide long-term benefits for their professional development.

Barriers:

A key challenge is ensuring trust in automation—employees need to be confident that forecasting models and automated scheduling will not negatively impact water supply operations. Resistance to change and concerns about reliability and intervention needs could slow adoption. Furthermore, employees may need additional training to fully integrate new flexibility strategies into their daily workflows.

IV.6.3.a.3. Energie Kompass GmbH (ENK)

Goals:

ENK's primary goal in this project is to develop and validate scalable flexibility solutions that allow municipal infrastructures, such as waterworks, to participate in energy markets. It seeks to demonstrate how industrial and municipal loads can be integrated into Virtual Power Plants (VPPs) and contribute to grid stability while creating new revenue streams through energy flexibility.

Drivers:

The increasing demand for flexibility in energy markets presents a strong driver for ENK, as waterworks represent a largely untapped source of controllable load. Technological advancements in demand-side management (DSM) and battery storage control create new business opportunities. Additionally, policy support for demand response and decentralized energy solutions incentivizes ENK to push for scalable, replicable models.

Barriers:

One of the key barriers is the lack of regulatory clarity on how public infrastructure can participate in flexibility markets. Additionally, data access and interoperability challenges can hinder real-time optimization efforts, as municipal utilities often use heterogeneous legacy systems. Risk aversion in public-sector clients also slows down the adoption of innovative energy strategies.

IV.6.3.a.4. Energienetze Burgenland GmbH (DSO)

Goals:

The distribution system operator (DSO) seeks to maintain grid stability while enabling more decentralized energy integration. The ability to manage peak loads and integrate flexible assets, such as waterworks, aligns with the DSO's efforts to reduce grid congestion and improve system efficiency.

Drivers:

The increasing penetration of renewable energy in Burgenland creates a need for flexible consumers to balance supply and demand. The potential to leverage municipal infrastructure as a demand-side resource aligns with European grid modernization goals. Additionally, regulatory frameworks, such as the EU Clean Energy Package, encourage DSOs to explore flexibility procurement mechanisms.

Barriers:

One of the main challenges is the lack of standardized mechanisms for DSOs to procure flexibility from municipal entities. The regulatory framework does not yet fully define how demand-side flexibility from public utilities can be compensated or integrated into grid balancing mechanisms. Additionally, technical challenges related to data exchange, latency in control signals, and verification of flexibility services present operational hurdles.

IV.6.3.a.5. Municipality of Oberwart

Goals:

The local government seeks to improve the sustainability and efficiency of municipal infrastructure while reducing energy costs for public services. Supporting innovative energy solutions aligns with broader climate goals and the municipality's efforts to position itself as a leader in smart city initiatives.

Drivers:

The municipality is driven by economic and environmental incentives to integrate more renewable energy and energy-efficient solutions into public operations. EU and national funding opportunities for sustainable infrastructure projects further encourage participation. Additionally, engaging in regional and European innovation projects enhances the municipality's visibility and access to expertise.

Barriers:

Public-sector decision-making processes tend to be slow and risk-averse, leading to delays in the adoption of new energy management solutions. Legal constraints, particularly in relation to public procurement and contracting, limit direct participation in alternative energy models such as peer-to-peer energy sharing. Additionally, budget constraints and competing municipal priorities can make energy innovation a secondary focus compared to core infrastructure needs.

IV.6.3.a.6. Citizens of the Oberwart Region

Goals:

The residents of Oberwart and surrounding municipalities rely on a stable, affordable, and sustainable water supply. Their main interest is that the operational efficiency of the waterworks remains high while avoiding excessive cost increases due to rising energy prices.

Drivers:

As energy costs impact municipal service fees, citizens have an interest in the cost-effective operation of public infrastructure. Public awareness of sustainability and climate action is growing, increasing support for local renewable energy utilization in municipal services. Additionally, reliable service from the WWSB ensures public trust, making it important that the water supply remains uninterrupted and resilient to grid disturbances.

Barriers:

Citizens have limited direct influence over energy decisions at the waterworks. Additionally, there is often low public awareness of the role that water infrastructure can play in energy system flexibility. Ensuring clear communication and transparency about the benefits of energy optimization at WWSB is key to maintaining public support.

IV.6.3.b. Current Stakeholder Communication Setup

The communication between stakeholders involved in the Waterworks Oberwart demonstration follows a structured approach, reflecting the multi-level governance and operational responsibilities of the participating entities. As a public-law association, the Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB) maintains direct communication with municipal authorities, regulatory bodies, and its operational partners, ensuring alignment with legal requirements and regional infrastructure planning. The decision-making process within WVSB is shaped by internal administrative structures and guided by public-sector regulations, particularly concerning procurement and financial planning.

On the technical and operational level, WVSB coordinates closely with Energie Kompass GmbH (ENK), the technology provider responsible for implementing smart energy solutions at the site. This collaboration involves regular working meetings, data-sharing protocols, and integration planning to ensure smooth implementation of demand-side management (DSM) and flexibility measures. ENK also serves as the primary interface between WVSB and energy market participants, including Energienetze Burgenland GmbH (the regional DSO), which oversees grid stability and the integration of decentralized flexibility resources. Communication with the DSO primarily revolves around technical feasibility, regulatory constraints, and potential market interactions for flexibility services.

The municipality of Oberwart, as a key regional stakeholder, engages in policy-level discussions regarding infrastructure modernization and energy transition efforts. While it does not play a direct role in daily operations, its involvement ensures that the project aligns with regional sustainability strategies and municipal climate action plans. Public communication is primarily managed through WVSB, which provides information about service reliability, operational efficiency, and sustainability efforts to the citizens of the Oberwart region. However, as energy flexibility is a relatively new concept for municipal infrastructure, public engagement and awareness-raising efforts remain limited.

Overall, stakeholder communication is structured but somewhat segmented, with each entity focusing on its primary responsibilities. While technical coordination is well established, further efforts could enhance cross-sector communication and public transparency, particularly regarding the long-term benefits of energy flexibility and demand-side management for municipal services.

IV.6.3.c. Current Social Fabric (e.g., sports groups, energy communities...)

The Waterworks Oberwart is embedded within the broader social and economic structure of the Oberwart region, which consists of a mix of urban and rural communities. As the administrative and economic center of southern Burgenland, Oberwart serves as a hub for regional commerce, public services, and social life. The municipality is home to various local associations, cultural initiatives, and sports clubs, which play a vital role in fostering community engagement and regional identity. Among these, football clubs, volunteer fire brigades, and cultural organizations contribute to a strong sense of local belonging and cooperation.

Municipal infrastructure, including the waterworks, is viewed as a public service rather than an active element of local engagement, meaning that awareness of its role in the energy transition remains limited. While the Wasserverband Südliches Burgenland (WVSB) is a crucial player in maintaining public utilities, it does not traditionally engage in broader community initiatives beyond ensuring water supply reliability. Unlike other municipal facilities, such as schools or community centers, the waterworks operates largely in the background of daily social life, with limited public interaction beyond occasional maintenance updates or service notices.

From an energy perspective, Oberwart has participated in Smart City and renewable energy projects (e.g., Loadshift Oberwart, USC Südburgenland, Innovation Lab act4.energy, Industry4Redispatch), but as of February 2025, WVSB is not yet a member of a Renewable Energy Community (REC) due to legal procurement constraints. While local businesses and private households increasingly participate in solar energy and energy-sharing initiatives, municipal infrastructure remains less integrated into these efforts.

Overall, the social fabric of Oberwart is characterized by active community life and growing sustainability awareness, though the role of municipal utilities in the energy transition is not yet widely recognized. Strengthening the connection between public services, energy innovation, and local engagement could

enhance public awareness of the benefits of flexibility, self-consumption, and sustainable energy management in the region.

IV.6.3.d. Vision

The Waterworks Oberwart serves as a critical infrastructure facility ensuring a reliable water supply to municipalities in the region. Its integration into flexibility markets aligns with the broader vision of optimizing municipal assets for demand-side flexibility, thereby reducing operational costs, enhancing grid stability, and contributing to the local energy transition.

This vision extends beyond technical upgrades, emphasizing the engagement of facility operators, municipal stakeholders, and market actors in a collaborative approach to leverage industrial-scale flexibility for sustainable energy management.

IV.6.3.e. Technical Building Flexibility

The Waterworks Oberwart will transform into a flexible energy asset by integrating its pumping station, battery storage, and PV system into an intelligent flexibility management framework. Through predictive analytics and day-ahead forecasting, the facility will optimize energy consumption patterns, actively participate in demand-side response (DSR) programs, and support grid stability through Virtual Power Plant (VPP) integration. The long-term vision is to establish a fully automated flexibility framework, ensuring seamless interaction between energy demand, storage, and grid requirements.

IV.6.3.f. Social Building Flexibility

The successful adoption of flexibility solutions requires a culture shift among facility operators and stakeholders. The vision is to foster trust in automated energy optimization by ensuring that staff and decision-makers recognize the benefits of autonomous flexibility scheduling. Through training, engagement, and continuous knowledge transfer, the waterworks will become a model for municipal energy flexibility, where technical innovation aligns with operational needs and staff confidence in digital energy solutions.

IV.6.3.g. Technical Infrastructure

The Waterworks Oberwart will be seamlessly integrated into a broader smart energy ecosystem, interacting with grid operators, digital platforms, and flexibility aggregators. By leveraging the BlueBird Platform, the waterworks will be able to dynamically schedule and optimize energy use based on real-time grid conditions, market signals, and operational constraints. The long-term goal is to create a replicable and scalable infrastructure model, demonstrating how municipal assets can evolve into flexibility hubs.

IV.6.3.h. Social Infrastructure

The vision extends beyond technology—creating an inclusive and cooperative environment where regulatory bodies, municipalities, and citizens understand and support flexibility integration. Through policy alignment, transparent stakeholder communication, and regulatory adaptation, the waterworks aims to become a fully compliant and legally integrated flexibility provider. By demonstrating the economic, operational, and environmental benefits of municipal flexibility, the waterworks will pave the way for similar public infrastructure sites to adopt energy flexibility as a standard practice.

IV.6.4. Use Cases

BC #6 Enlion

- UC 6.1** Prediction and scheduling of waterworks power consumption
- UC 6.2** Optimize the use of the retention tank as flexibility / storage to generate actuations
- UC 6.3** Utilize the VPP to maximize potential for marketing flexibilities

Figure 52: UC Overview: ENK/Enlion

UC 6.1 Prediction and scheduling of waterworks power consumption

Predict the total electricity demand and supply; i.e., the energy demand from the water pumps and the energy supply from the PV (100 KW peak) as well as the net intake from the electricity grid, taking into account the current operation of the battery (300 KWh), the current operation of the water pumps, the weather forecast and the water demand forecast.

UC 6.2 Optimize the use of the retention tank as flexibility / storage to generate actuations

Upgrade the building’s automation system to allow inclusion of water storage tanks operation into flexibility scheme. Optimization of the waterworks operation and scheduling and sending according signals to staff.

UC 6.3 Utilize the VPP to maximize potential for marketing flexibilities

Improve Virtual Power Plant (VPP) capability and functionality. The VPP, operated by ENK, shall be upgraded to be able to participate both in unregulated as well as regulated flexibility markets. It includes to deploy and implement market interfaces to the TSO and certify flexibility assets for regulated flexibility markets.

Interface is provided by TSO; the idea is to connect, register, then have an interface where to place flex bids on several flex markets. One result might be a set of recommendations for regulation in other member states!

IV.6.5. Implementation Plan and Current Status of Implementation

Here is an excerpt from the implementation plan until beginning of February; the full implementation plan can be found in the appendix.

Figure 53: ENK implementation plan timeline

Current Status of Implementation

Although data needed have been identified, at M13 there is still no data available to start forecasting, building the DT and the optimization model; although a rough version of the optimization formula has been generated.

A set of tasks that were possible to be implemented without the knowledge of data, mainly the setting up and extension of the VPP have been executed in time.

Integrating the BlueBird system with the legacy system at the waterworks has not yet been started, but guidelines of the interaction have been set up. KPIs have been defined and the regulatory framework has been mapped to the pilot plans, provided by WP7.

IV.6.6. Pilot Specific KPIs

Table 24: Pilot Specific KPIs ENK

ID	Name	Formula	Temporal Granularity	Legend
ENK 1	Number of validated flexibility requests from markets	$N_{flex,req}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{n(t)} 1$	Yearly	$N_{flex,req}(t)$ – validated flexibility requests
ENK 2	Market revenues from flexibility provision	$R_{flex}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{m(t)} (E_{flex,i} \cdot P_{flex,i})$	Yearly	$R_{flex}(t)$ – market revenues; $E_{flex,i}$ – provided flexibility energy; $P_{flex,i}$ – market price
ENK 3	Number of load changes effected by flexibility provision	$N_{load,exec}^{valid}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{n(t)} \mathbb{1}(req_i \in V) \cdot \mathbb{1}(LC_i = executed)$	Event based	$N_{load,exec}^{valid}(t)$ – validated & executed load changes; LC_i – load change status; $\mathbb{1}(\cdot)$ – indicator function
ENK 4	Operating costs of flexibility provision	$OC_{flex}(t) = C_{energy,shift}(t) + C_{operation}(t) + C_{ICT}(t) + C_{dep,flex}(t)$	Event based	$OC_{flex}(t)$ – total operating costs; $C_{energy,shift}(t)$ – energy shifting costs; $C_{operation}(t)$ – operational costs; $C_{ICT}(t)$ – ICT/system costs; $C_{dep,flex}(t)$ – depreciation

General Indices and Sets

- t – Considered time period (yearly or event-based)
- i – Running index for individual requests, transactions, or events
- $n(t)$ – Number of flexibility requests in period t
- $m(t)$ – Number of marketed flexibility transactions in period St
- V – Set of validated flexibility requests
- req_i – i -th flexibility request

Number of validated flexibility requests

- $N_{flex,req}(t)$ – Number of validated flexibility requests in period t

Market revenues from flexibility provision

- $R_{flex}(t)$ – Market revenues from flexibility provision in period t
- $E_{flex,i}$ – Provided flexibility energy of transaction i
- $P_{flex,i}$ – Market price of transaction i

Number of load changes effected by flexibility provision

- $N_{load,exec}^{valid}(t)$ – Number of validated and executed load changes in period t
- LC_i – Status of load change related to request i
- $1(\cdot)$ – Indicator function (1 if the condition is fulfilled, otherwise 0)

Operating costs of flexibility provision

- $OC_{flex}(t)$ – Total operating costs of flexibility provision in period t
- $C_{energy,shift}(t)$ – Energy shifting costs
- $C_{operation}(t)$ – Operational costs
- $C_{ICT}(t)$ – ICT/system costs
- $C_{dep,flex}(t)$ – Depreciation of flexibility assets

IV.7. EWH: Hotels with PV, biomass driven CHP and charging stations

IV.7.1. General Business Case Information

IV.7.1.a. Buildings and Local Context

IV.7.1.a.1. Hotel Prinz-Luitpold-Bad (PLB): Type and features

The **Hotel Prinz-Luitpold-Bad** is a four-star wellness hotel nestled in the Bavarian Alps. The hotel boasts a rich history, with the first buildings on the site dating back to the 1860s. The current owners, the Gross family, acquired the hotel in 1923 and have since meticulously developed and expanded the estate. While the hotel retains some of its original structures, it is continually evolving. Over the years, balconies and terraces have been added, new buildings have been constructed, and the wellness facilities have been significantly expanded. This ongoing development ensures the hotel remains at the forefront of luxury and comfort.

The hotel features 83 rooms and can accommodate up to 200 guests. Additionally, 8 of the 70 employees are housed in a separate accommodation for staff. Guests can enjoy a wide range of wellness amenities, including both an indoor and an outdoor pool, as well as a whirlpool. The extensive sauna area offers three different saunas, a steam room, an infrared rooms and a cold chamber. For relaxation, the spa area includes several relaxation rooms with heated water beds, infrared beds, and an exercise room.

The hotel is sustainably heated by two pellet heaters and three combined heat and power (CHP) plants, which also provide warmth to the indoor and outdoor swimming pools. The saunas are heated electrically. In addition to the CHP plants, the hotel generates electricity through a south-facing roof-mounted photovoltaic system. Recently six private EV Chargers have been installed.

Figure 54: Hotel Prinz Luitpold-Bad

IV.7.1.a.2. Hostel JuBi: Type and features

The **Jugendausbildungsstätte Hindelang (JuBi)** is a hostel and youth training facility owned by the German Alpine Association, the **Deutscher Alpenverein (DAV)**. It primarily hosts DAV workshop groups of all ages, as well as school class trips. The DAV is the world's largest climbing association, comprising 356 regional sections. It promotes alpine sports through the operation of huts in the Alps, climbing gyms across Germany, and an extensive program of workshops and training to educate and promote alpine sports.

The building, originally constructed in 1933 as a hotel, was acquired by the DAV in 1990. Subsequently, it underwent significant renovations in 1993 and 2011, expanding and modernizing the facility while preserving its historical character. Today, the property offers 103 beds and is managed by 25 employees. In addition to overseeing the hostel, the team organizes a variety of educational programs. The facility also includes five conference rooms, an exercise area, and a dining hall with an accompanying kitchen.

The building is heated by an 80 kW pellet heater, supported by solar thermal panels. Electricity is supplied from the grid. Plans for photovoltaic (PV) installations were cancelled due to heritage protection regulations. Recently, four public EV chargers were installed.

Figure 55: JuBi

IV.7.1.a.3. Local Context

The two buildings are situated in close proximity in Bad Hindelang, a picturesque community in the Bavarian Alps, located within the Allgäu region. They are positioned on the south-facing mountain side of the valley. The area attracts tourists from around the globe, with tourism serving as a cornerstone of the local economy. A nearby ski resort draws visitors in the winter, while in the warmer months, a wealth of hiking, climbing, and biking opportunities in the surrounding mountains is a major draw. This strong dependence on nature as a key business asset has led to a certain reluctance toward large-scale investments in renewable energy, such as wind, solar, or hydro power, as they are perceived to negatively impact the landscape.

The Elektrizitätswerk Hindelang eG (EWH) serves as a prime example of the community spirit that defines the valley. Founded in 1923 by a group of local citizens, the cooperative has proudly provided sustainable and independent energy for the region for over a century. Understanding the social fabric and dynamics of the local community is crucial for fostering any form of change or progress in the area. The community is closely knit, with strong bonds and long-standing resentments that can significantly hinder or even halt construction projects. Therefore, careful consideration of local values and perspectives is essential for the success of any initiatives.

IV.7.1.b. Current SRI

IV.7.1.b.1. Prinz-Luitpold-Bad building (PLB)

SRI original EU Version at M4 in the project: (versus SRI 24,4% from proposal)

Figure 56: Original SRI Prinz Luitpold-Bad

SRI BlueBird Version at M4:

Figure 57: SRI Prinz Luitpold-Bad at M4

Figure 58: Figure 59: SRI Proposal Prinz Luitpold-Bad

IV.7.1.b.2. JuBi building

SRI original EU Version at M4 in the project:

Figure 60: Original SRI JuBi

SRI BlueBird Version at M4 in the project:

Figure 61: SRI Jubi at M4

IV.7.1.c. Stakeholder Overview

The main stakeholders involved in the EWH demonstration within the BlueBird project include the following:

- **Armin Gross** – The owner of the Hotel Prinz Luitpold Bad and Share holder/Member of EWH.
- **Prinz Luitpold Bad Employees**
- **Prinz Luitpold Bad Guests** – The hotel guests can vary between long term regular customers or first time guests. However they are generally more wealthy.
- **Jugendausbildungsstätte Hindelang (JuBi) Management**
- **JuBi Employees**
- **JuBi Guests** – The Hostel Guests can vary from school children aged 10-18 on a class trip with their teacher to a group of adults in a weeklong workshop to acquire a trainer certificate.
- **External EV Drivers** – Any EV driver in Hindelang that decides to use the public EV charging stations outside the JuBi.
- **Elektrizitätswerk Hindelang eG** - grid operator and electricity provider

IV.7.1.d. Legal Framework

The **Energiewirtschaftsgesetz (EnWG)** is Germany's main set of laws for regulating electricity and gas supply. Recent changes bring a set of major challenges to DSOs, who in the future will have to be able to monitor and control major consumers and network connections to ensure grid safety. This applies to all consumers in the grid that can draw more than 4,2 kW which obviously includes the charging stations installed at the two demo buildings.

The **Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (EEG)** ensures producers of renewable energy receive compensation for the energy they produce. Reforms to this regulation were planned for 2025, but it is uncertain whether the new government will implement them or propose a new set of changes. This is a point of uncertainty, as it is unclear how renewable energy production will be controlled and compensated in the coming years.

The **Gebäude-Energie-Gesetz (GEG)** defines energy efficiency regulations for buildings in Germany.

The **Gebäude-Elektromobilitätsinfrastruktur-Gesetz (GEIG)** is the set of laws defining how charging infrastructure for parking spaces is built.

IV.7.2. Technical Infrastructure Prinz Luitpold Bad

IV.7.2.a. Heat

IV.7.2.a.1. Physical Infrastructure: Type of heating/cooling, energy sources, grid

The building's heating is provided by two pellet heaters and three liquid gas Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants. Additionally, there is an emergency/peak load oil heater installed, which is rarely used. All produced heat is fed into a 25 cubic meter buffer tank and distributed from there. These heating systems not only supply warmth to the rooms but are also responsible for heating both the indoor and outdoor swimming pools. Cooling is provided by a compound refrigeration system equipped with three compressors. This system is used to cool the air conditioning as well as the refrigeration systems in the kitchen.

The produced waste heat is used to warm water. Domestic Hot water is supplied by five boilers: four located in the main building and one in the employee accommodation.

IV.7.2.a.2. Energy mix for heating

In 2023, most of the building's heat was produced by the pellet heaters, accounting for 62% of the total heat generation. The Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants contributed 37%, while approximately 1% of the heat was supplied by oil.

IV.7.2.a.3. What can be controlled?

The pellet heater and CHP plant are controlled by separate control systems. While reprogramming of the two assets to enable data logging and control through Bluebird services is possible, the cost would exceed EWHs Budget. Therefore, they are not controllable in the scope of the Bluebird Project.

IV.7.2.a.4. Data availability

There is no data logging in the Prinz Luitpold Bad heating system.

IV.7.2.b. Electricity

IV.7.2.b.1. Physical Infrastructure:

The building is equipped with 350 square meters of solar panels, providing a peak output of 70 kW. In addition to the photovoltaic system, the Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants generate approximately 40 kW of electricity. The remaining power is supplied via the grid by EWH.

Energy consumers include the saunas and other spa facilities, as well as the kitchen, which is equipped with numerous high-power appliances. Additionally, pumps for the heating system and the compressors for the cooling of the 7 cold storage rooms contribute to the building's overall energy demand.

IV.7.2.b.2. Energy mix for electricity

In 2023, the building's electricity consumption was primarily sourced from the Combined Heat and Power (CHP) plants, which generated 55% of the total electricity used. The grid supplied around 35% of the electricity and the PV around 10%.

IV.7.2.b.3. What can be controlled?

The most promising energy consumers are the cold storage rooms. The cooling compressors are controlled based on the demand of the storage rooms which are controlled by a 2 two-point temperature controller. This controller is capable of Modbus communication which can be used to read data and send commands like temperature setpoints to control the system. The kitchen appliances by rational could be controlled but only via the proprietary rational software. Major spa consumers control is either manual or through timer and Minor spa consumers like heated infra-red beds or can be controlled by the customers on demand.

IV.7.2.b.4. Data availability

Table 25: Data availability EWH Electricity

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
CHP and solar surplus [kW]	15 min	Whole building	historic	EWH
Solar generation [kW]	15 min	Whole building	historic	EWH
Grid Load Profile [KW]	15 min	Whole Building	historic	EWH
Refrigeration cell inside temperature, outside temperature	1 min	Each cell	Periodic after technology upgrade	EWH
Refrigeration Cell door status	On event	Each cell	Periodic after technology upgrade	EWH

IV.7.2.c. EVs

IV.7.2.c.1. Physical Infrastructure: Type of charging stations and protocol

The hotel parking lot is equipped with four private charging stations. The stations are AMTRON Professional+ 22 C2 chargers by Mennekes. These charging stations are integrated into the EWH's load

management system via Modbus, and invoicing is managed by the service provider ChargeCloud.

IV.7.2.c.2. Energy sources and energy mix for electricity

The charging stations are supplied by the grid of EWH and are not connected to the building's PV system since they have a separate grid connection from the building.

IV.7.2.c.3. What can be controlled?

EWH can control the available power at each of the stations over its Modbus load management system. Furthermore, the AMTRON Professional wall boxes are OCPP 1.6 compatible. OCPP could be used to control the charging stations for smart charging with the use of charging profiles. OCPP is already used by commercial smart charging actors.

IV.7.2.c.4. Data availability

Table 26: Data availability EWH EV

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Chargecloud data for charging processes. Total kwh consumption	Start stop times	Each station	From installation in 2022 onwards.	EWH
Load profile of Grid connection point	Roughly 15 minutes	Whole Grid Connection point	Periodc after technology upgrade	EWH

IV.7.3. Technical Infrastructure JuBi

IV.7.3.a. Heat

IV.7.3.a.1. Physical Infrastructure: Type of heating/cooling, energy sources, grid

The building is equipped with an 80 kW pellet heater, along with pumps and a heating control system that operates based on a heating curve. The control system is accessible through a computer which the staff uses to manually deactivate or manipulate the heating control in edge cases. There are potential plans to upgrade the control system in 2025/2026.

Additionally, solar thermal panels are installed, although they are not operational during the winter months and produce nearly excessive heat during the summer. For peak demand, a gas burner is used to supplement the heating system.

IV.7.3.a.2. Energy mix for heating

The Pellet Heater produces around 81%, the solar thermal panels around 8 % and the Gas burner around 11% of the heat used in the building.

IV.7.3.a.3. What can be controlled?

There is control software for heaters and pumps based on a heating curve. There are currently no ways of feeding in external control software.

IV.7.3.a.4. Data availability

There is no data logging in the Jubi heating system

IV.7.3.b. Electricity

IV.7.3.b.1. Physical Infrastructure

The building's electricity is supplied by the EWH grid. While there have been plans to install photovoltaic (PV) systems, building regulations have prevented implementation over the past several years. Major energy consumers include the heating circuit pumps, booster pumps, and kitchen appliances.

IV.7.3.b.2. Energy mix for electricity

100% of the Electricity is supplied through the Grid.

IV.7.3.b.3. What can be controlled?

Heating-related electrical consumers are controlled through the heating system control described earlier, while devices such as the booster pumps run continuously. All other electrical consumers are operated manually or through indirect human activation like motion sensors for lighting. There is no control through Bluebird possible.

IV.7.3.b.4. Data availability

Table 27: Data availability JuBi Electricity

Data [Name] [Unit]	and Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Grid Load Profile [KW]	15 min	Whole Building	historic	EWH

IV.7.3.c. EVs

IV.7.3.c.1. Physical Infrastructure: Type of charging stations and protocol

In the JuBi parking lot two ABL eMH3 TWIN charging stations are installed. These support AC charging of two vehicles each, with up to 22kW. The Charging stations are operated by the service provider Chargecloud who handles billing.

IV.7.3.c.2. Energy sources and energy mix for electricity

The energy is supplied by the grid of EWH.

IV.7.3.c.3. What can be controlled?

The ABL eMH3 TWIN wall boxes are OCPP 1.6 compatible. OCPP could be used to control the charging stations for smart charging with the use of charging profiles. OCPP is already used by commercial smart charging actors.

IV.7.3.c.4. Data availability

Table 28: Data availability JuBi EV

Data [Name] and [Unit]	Temporal Granularity	Location Granularity	Historic? Period?	Access via [Name]
Chargecloud data for charging processes. Total kwh consumption	Start stop times	Each station	From installation in 2022 onwards.	EWH

IV.7.4. Social Infrastructure

IV.7.4.a. Stakeholders’ Goals, Drivers, and Barriers

IV.7.4.a.1. Hotel Owner

Goals:

Armin Gross aims to continue his family's hotel as a profitable business that provides high-standard services to its customers. At the same time, his personal belief is that luxury hotels only have justification to exist if customers do not emit more CO₂ equivalents during their stay than they would at home. Therefore, he is always looking to improve his hotel's sustainability while ensuring the reliability and quality of his services. From a project perspective, Armin Gross would need to be convinced to invest in more automation of services like room heating or energy-optimized spa operations.

Drivers:

His personal beliefs and business strategy described above are the main drivers. A potential financial benefit through flexible electricity tariffs and a curiosity about technology are additional motivators.

Barriers:

As described above, the legal framework and building regulations can hinder development. Furthermore, customer satisfaction must be ensured and cannot be compromised from his perspective. Lastly, the current control technology of the hotel offers limited opportunities for automation, and construction is mostly restricted to very short windows during the year when the hotel is closed. As a result, implementing changes in technology is challenging.

IV.7.4.a.2. Prinz-Luitpold-Bad Employees

Goals:

From a project perspective, Luitpold Bad employees should assist with two possible flexibility changes in the hotel. First, there is the conversion of charging services to help customers charge their EVs during optimal periods, where staff may play a role in the implementation. Second, there is the optimization of the use of high-power appliances in the industrial kitchen, where the staff's working patterns would be affected.

Drivers:

A possible driver for the staff would be financial incentives.

Barriers:

Unlike the owner, the staff cannot be expected to have any personal drive or interest in flexibility. It is more likely that there will be reluctance toward change. There is most likely no prior knowledge about the workings of the energy industry or the need for flexibility. Furthermore, staff in the hotel industry in Germany are already in short supply. Introducing work-intensive measures will most likely face resistance or may be impossible due to workload constraints. Lastly, existing work patterns and habits could hinder the willingness to embrace change.

IV.7.4.a.3. Prinz-Luitpold-Bad Guests**Goals:**

The guests visit the hotel for vacation, relaxation, and high-quality wellness facilities. They are also willing to pay the price for the high level of comfort provided at the hotel. To increase flexibility, hotel guests would have to relinquish control over their EV charging or accept changes to hotel services, such as spa opening times.

Drivers:

Personal motivations toward the environment could be Drivers. In general, suitable incentives for guests still must be explored.

Barriers:

Since these hotel guests are willing to pay a high price for comfort, it must be seen as a high priority. Any measure that reduces comfort will most likely not be accepted. A hotel guest with an EV might not fully relax until it is charged. To gain flexibility from hotel guest EV charging, good communication and reliable services must be provided to avoid compromising guest satisfaction.

IV.7.4.a.4. JuBi Employees**Goals:**

Jubi employees can be divided into two categories. The first group is responsible for managing the facility, as well as planning and executing the educational programs and workshops provided to guests. This group is motivated to work with the project partners to educate guests about flexibility. The second group consists of staff tasked with general operational duties around the hostel. Here, personal engagement with the project is less likely.

Drivers:

The first group is more likely to be personally motivated to act in an environmentally or energetically positive way. They are personally invested in climate change and general environmental issues.

Barriers:

Upon initial observation, the working processes of this staff group appear quite rigid, offering little room for flexibility. Furthermore, most of the technology is quite old, and even in recent upgrades, smart features were not considered.

IV.7.4.a.5. JuBi Guests**Goals:**

There are two flexibility measures applicable to the JuBi guests. The first is peak shaving, which can be achieved either through technology or by influencing user behaviour. The second measure involves the

guests' EV charging behaviour. While there is potential to optimize the charging process, it is important to note that there are still very few guests with electric vehicles at this facility.

Drivers:

Older guests (16 and above) are more likely to have a personal interest in climate change and environmental issues, which could serve as a potential driver for engagement. In contrast, younger guests (ages 10-18) can likely be motivated with small incentives.

Barriers:

The guests use of the building services can never really be shifted into optimal time windows during mid-day, as they are almost never inside the building during the day.

IV.7.4.a.6. External EV Drivers

Goals:

External EV drivers are non-guests who use the public chargers installed in the JuBi parking lot. The goal is to encourage them to charge during optimal time windows. Achieving this could involve intraday planning and education to encourage day-ahead planning to align their charging schedules with the most energy-efficient periods.

Drivers:

Possible drivers to change charging behaviour could be financial benefits or good conscience.

Barriers:

There is limited incentive for EV drivers to charge at this location unless they are in urgent need of charging. The area lacks amenities and has relatively few hiking trails nearby. Additionally, it is expected that external drivers will primarily use the charging station as a one-time stop. As a result, education efforts may have minimal impact on changing behavior at this charging point.

IV.7.4.a.7. Elektrizitätswerk Hindelang eG

Goals:

EWH aims to strengthen its local presence and retain its important customers through the development of new products and energy services. The plan is to pass on lower electricity purchase costs to customers and reduce pressure on its own grid.

Drivers:

Long-term financial benefits from flexibility measures are key drivers of this initiative. Additionally, alignment with the company's strategic goals is an important factor in driving these efforts forward.

Barriers:

Technology barriers, such as mismatched interfaces or security vulnerabilities, may hinder progress. There is also a reliance on the hotels as external partners, who must allow experimental measures to be implemented within their facilities. Lastly, regulatory barriers exist; for example, the aforementioned EnWG does not foresee cooperation between the DSO and sales.

IV.7.4.b. Current Stakeholder Communication Setup

The Hotel Prinz-Luitpold-Bad and the JuBi are both customers of EWH. EWH has already established direct contact with key staff members, including those responsible for building technology. All other communication will take place through the respective managers. For now, EWH will act as the main point of contact between the project partners and the two demo entities. Direct interactions between WP4 and

other stakeholders, such as conducting surveys, may be possible. Similar interactions with other entities can also be considered, but they must be coordinated with EWH and the relevant managers.

IV.7.4.c. Current Social Fabric

As outlined in the local context chapter, the community is tightly knit and personal reputation carries significant weight. This situation benefits the Luitpold Bad, which enjoys a strong reputation, but poses challenges for JuBi, which has struggled with its local image for over a decade. Hotels in the region are well-connected, and information about new technologies is regularly shared. The PLB is regarded as a leader and role model for the region's sustainable transition within the hospitality industry.

EWH, operating as a cooperative, maintains strong connections with the hotels participating in this project, other hotels throughout the valley, and key stakeholders such as the municipality—all of whom are members of the cooperative.

IV.7.5. Vision

EWH's vision is to provide a sustainable, local, and community-oriented energy supply. Flexibility may be a key aspect in the transition toward renewable energy, supporting the creation of a reliable, competitive, and resilient supply for the region.

Given the significant role of hotels in the local economy, and consequently in EWH's business, an analysis of the flexibility potential in these buildings is planned. The goal is to develop measures that enhance adaptability, resulting in financial benefits that can be passed on to customers, thereby strengthening the region and securing EWH's position in the local market.

In addition, the rapid expansion of EV charging infrastructure in the valley has been identified as a potential risk to the local grid. To address this, EWH aims to gain greater control over the infrastructure and implement technologies that optimize charging not only from a financial standpoint but also in terms of grid stability.

IV.7.5.a. Technical Building Flexibility

Through the implementation of smart charging technology, the building's largest consumers will be able to participate in flexible energy markets. This is particularly effective in the hotel sector, as guests often park their vehicles for multiple days, providing extended time windows for optimization. There are also plans to increase the flexibility of the building's kitchen cold storage units.

Measures such as the integration of smart charging systems will help transform the building to better meet the future demands of the energy market. This will reduce peak loads on the grid, lowering the pressure for costly local grid upgrades. Additionally, energy procurement costs can be reduced through improved consumption control, resulting in financial benefits.

IV.7.5.b. Social Building Flexibility

The two objects in this demo site are located close to each other and attract guests for similar reasons, such as the appeal of the surrounding alpine region. However, they cater to very different types of visitors. The JuBi offers insight not only into children's perceptions of flexibility measures but also into those of adults of all ages who are personally motivated to minimize their environmental impact. In contrast, the Prinz-Luitpold-Bad tends to attract more affluent guests, for whom monetary incentives may be less effective. This difference will provide valuable insight into the differences between different demographics in relation to flexibility potentials.

Before implementing social flexibility measures that might influence the guest experience, a deeper understanding of guest motivations toward energy flexibility is needed.

IV.7.5.c. Technical Infrastructure

The site consists of two buildings constructed around 100 years ago. Although the building technology in both structures has been upgraded in recent years, their smart readiness remains very low compared to modern buildings.

This project will demonstrate what improvements are possible in existing buildings in terms of digitalization and automation. The goal is to determine whether simple control system upgrades can unlock significant flexibility potential, or if more extensive building technology upgrades are required.

IV.7.6. Use Cases

Figure 62: UC Overview: EWH

UC 7.1 Prediction of cold rooms and EV electricity demand, PV electricity supply and other external forecasts

Build DT of the Cold Storage Rooms and the Refrigeration Compressors, considering thermal behaviour, door opening and compressor activation. And create DT of Charging Stations based on traffic and user arrival pattern. Provide forecasts of PV Generation 110 kW at PLB.

UC 7.2 Optimization of cold rooms operation taking account of PV generation and the current electricity price

The cold rooms in the hotel need to be operated in a way that hygienic temperature requirements for the food are met, but at the same time electricity draw from the grid is minimized, taking into account PV and CHP production (is CHP electricity production exogenous). If Electricity is drawn from the grid, this should be performed price optimized taking into account dynamic electricity prices. Both prepared dishes and ingredients for dishes are stored at different levels of temperature. Different cold rooms have different usage and requirements. Staff operate cold rooms by opening the doors to take or add food.

UC 7.3 Optimization and generation of recommendations and smart charging actuations for EV CS utilization taking account of the electricity price

EV CS operation is upgraded with smart charging algorithms and information for the generation of recommendations for EV drivers among the guests (UC 7.4) are provided.

UC 7.4 Interaction use case Implement Social and technological optimizations

The hotel owns 4 charging stations provided to their guests. Often guest come and plug in the car and start charging without consider extra cost they are causing due to high/low market prices when they pay a flat rate or unaware of grid constraints. This should be mitigated by offering smart charging inside guests temporary and State of Charge constraints or issuing recommendations for "good" charging times. UC 7.3 deals with the integration of smart charging into the system and prepares the information necessary to generate recommendations for the guests. This use case takes this as an input to formulate recommendations and creates a system to interact with the EV drivers among the hotel guests.

UC 7.5 Combined Control of the Hotels Flexible assets

Use case 7.2 and 7.3 evaluate the flexibility of the Assets in the Hotel individually. We do this because the charging stations are on an individual grid connection and therefore PV self-consumed etc. cannot be performed from a billing/regulatory point of view.

However, it is still interesting to explore the combination of the assets in a more complex control and the effects of this compared to the individual solutions.

UC 7.6 Simulate: Analyse Effects of Flexible Assets on Grid

Assuming that PV generation and charging infrastructure will cause the greatest stress on the EWH grid this UC uses the DTs to simulate at which kWp PV and kWp charging infrastructure we reach the limit of our 300kW transformer that the hotel is connected to and how we can enable greater expansion of the technologies with flexible control of the charging infrastructure.

UC 7.7 "OPTIONAL STUDY OF FEASIBILITY: Simulating the Aggregation of Multiple Hotels and their assets to participate on Flexibility Markets"

Next to Evaluating Business opportunities from exploiting implicit flexibility on the day ahead and intraday market we want to explore the opportunities for aggregating Hotels flexible assets to participate on regulation markets.

Two Markets are possible candidates:

- The Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR), requires fast actuation. The whole flexibility has to be activated in under 30 seconds. A benefit is it only has to be activated for a maximum of 15 minutes. However, it requires symmetric assets, able to increase or decrease Power. Here an analysis of the assets current behaviour and simulations with the digital twin have to show whether it will be possible to provide this.
- The other market it the automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR). Here the assets have to be activated less fast (30s-5min) and you can offer asymmetric load (e.g., only a decrease). However, this has to be made available for 4h time windows.

An analysis of the system and simulation will have to show whether this is possible with cold storage and Charging.

IV.7.7. Implementation Plan and Current Implementation Status

Here is an excerpt from the implementation plan until beginning of February 2026; the full implementation plan can be found in the appendix.

Figure 63: EWH implementation plan timeline

Current Implementation Status

This pilot focuses on two sets of UCs in two different buildings. Therefore, the focus was laid on one UC (the smart EV charging SC) in one pilot (the Hotel Prinz Luitpold PLB). For that, a set of historical data has been supplied and charging session patterns analysed. Also, a technology partner has been determined, a user experiment designed and a user story created which includes mockups of a corresponding GUI. At M13, the development of the according smart charging algorithms is under way, and all activities are in-line with the planning.

However, this is not the same for the other UC and pilot site: the JuBi hostel (Jubi) UCs have been neglected, no data extracted, no algorithms been created and only very preliminary discussions about user experiments have been conducted. This poses the risk of completion of the UCs during the project phase; however, this pilot has planned a big set of UCs compared to others.

Finally, the installation of sensors for the monitoring of the cold storage has been not yet been completed, neither in the one, nor in the other building, so that data collection could not be set up.

IV.7.8. Pilot Specific KPIs

Table 29: Pilot Specific KPIs EWH

ID	Name	Formula	Temporal Granularity
EWH 1	Cold Storage Energy Consumption increase	$E_{flex,inc} = E_{flex} - E_{base}$ E_{flex} : measured energy consumption during flexible operation E_{base} : Simulated or historical (limited data) energy consumption during normal operation	Annually, monthly
EWH 2	Cold Storage flexible Load per installed load Factor	$F_{flexofinstalled} = (\max_{4h} (P_{flex_operation,t} - P_{baseline,t})) / P_{installed}$ Determine how much kW flexibility per installed kW compressorpower the flexible operation provides in contrast to the baseline operation. you could calculate this for every 15 minutes or daily but we opted for a 4h used for flexibility reserves.	Time series of .. , 4h max or daily max
EWH 3	% of flex acceptance	$\%flexcharge = \#flex \text{ charging processes} / \#charging \text{ processes}$ $\#flexchargingprocesses$: number of charging processes where users opted into providing flexibility $\#charging \text{ processes}$: total number of charging process at the hotel	annual

EWH 4	Eflex	$E_{flex} = E_{flex} / E_{base}$ <p>E_{flex}: energy consumed in flexible charging process</p> <p>E_{base}: energy consumed in regular charging process with same start time</p>	Per charging process
EWH 5	Tflex	$T_{flex} = (t_{flex} - t_{start}) / (t_{departure} - t_{start})$ <p>t_{flex}: end of charging operation in flexible charging process</p> <p>t_{departure}: departure of vehicle</p>	Per charging process

V. LITERATURE

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VI. APPENDIX

The appendix contains more detailed information about the implementation plans. These have been exported at the beginning of February 2026 from the MIRO board, where they have been created and updated iteratively during the implementation phase.

VI.1. Pilot #1 KARNO

#1 Karno

Title, Task Description	Status September 2025	Support WPs	Start Date	End Date	Priority
Business Case Analysis, "Understanding and structuring the Business Case of Karno (Globally, UCs, needs, etc)	Completed	WP2	2025-01	2025-07	High
KPI Definition, "Define and precise the KPI to assess the success of the project	In Progress	WP2	2025-03	2025-12	Medium
System Modelization, "Providing information to modelize (digital twin) the hybrid system (aéro + géo HP) and the thermal energy network	Not Started	WP3	2025-09	2025-12	High
Digital Twin Test, "Establishing some case to test (inputs) and compare the digital twin and the reality (outputs)	Not Started	WP3	2025-12	2025-12	
Technical forecast definition, "Definition of the forecast needed, how to compute them and which source of data are used.	Not Started	WP3	2025-11	2025-12	
Technical Forecast Review and Improvement, "Based on what we've learned from the test, defining if we need to adapt the source of data for forecast and the way we forecast the data in order to get a more precised model	Not Started	WP3	2026-07	2026-10	
Digital Twin Improvement, "Based on what we've learned from the test, improving the digital twin in order to get a more precised model	Not Started	WP3	2026-07	2026-10	
Technical Forecast Evaluation and Analysis, "Evaluate the accuracy of the forecast	Not Started	WP3	2027-07	2027-12	
Digital Twin Evaluation and Analysis, "Evaluate the DT performance and	Not Started	WP3	2027-07	2027-12	

accuracy and analyse the results of the optimisation made from it					
User Interaction Tool Implementation, "Communicating and explaining to the users how to use the User Interaction Tool, what we expect from them and what gain they have to participate to it.	Not Started	WP4	2026-01	2026-01	
User Interaction Tool Review and Improvement, "The test observations indicate a need to improve the design of this UIT and enhance our communication/explanation to secure greater user emphasis (or engagement)	Not Started	WP4	2026-07	2026-10	
User Interaction Evaluation and Analysis, "Analysis the Users emphasis and the efficiency of the methods used for it. Report it	Not Started	WP4	2027-07	2027-12	
User Interaction Tool Definition, "Defining what is our need for a tool to communicate with the final users	In Progress	WP4-6	2025-09	2025-10	
Price Forecast definition, "Define how to predict the different price of electricity that will be inputs data for the model	Not Started	WP5	2025-11	2025-12	
Price Forecast Review and Improvement, "Based on what we've learned from the test, defining if we need to adapt the way we forecast the data in order to get a more precise model	Not Started	WP5	2026-07	2026-10	
Price Forecast Evaluation and Analysis, "Evaluate the accuracy of the forecast	Not Started	WP5	2027-07	2027-12	
Flexibility Analysis, "Based on our observations and past data, assess the opportunity of expanding this case to the flexibility market to determine the economic interest of such a model to play with the electricity flexibility market	Not Started	WP5	2027-07	2027-09	Low
User Interaction Tool Building, "Building the Interaction Tool on Karno's User Interface and make sure the users will have an easy access to it	Not Started	WP6	2025-11	2025-12	

IT integration, "Integration of all the BlueBird modules (Forecast + Digital Twins + requests + implementation + user tool) with dockers in the Karno current infrastructure	Not Started	WP6	2026-01	2026-01	
IT Integration Review and Improvement, "Review the way all the modules are integrated and think of ways of improving the integration	Not Started	WP6	2026-07	2026-10	
IT Integration Evaluation and Analysis, "Review the way all the modules were integrated and report it	Not Started	WP6	2027-07	2027-12	
Exploitation and Business Strategy, "Working on how expand this demo to other case"	Not Started	WP7	2027-07	2027-09	
Extension Network Study, "Providing data and helping the WP in charge of this study:"; - defining data needed; - collecting the data; - running the analysis; " - present the results	Not Started	tbd	2027-07	2027-09	
Remote Control, "Roll Supervision & final version of the remote control. Temporary control of machines in the energy center needed to be updated with a real remote control, owned by KARNO. Then, from the office, setpoints can be manipulated directly";	In Progress		2025-09		Medium
Aerothermal Heat Pump, "Change of aerothermal HP: type is selected, was slow during vacation.	In Progress		2025-05	2025-09	High
Meters, "Add electricity & heat meters on each HP"; will deliver more accurate data. COP is only global for the whole system, but without additional meters, digging deeper is impossible.	Not Started		2025-10		Need to fix a date""; Medium
PV installation					
,"PV installation: currently blocked by DSO - waiting for improvement to install.	In Progress		2025-09		Waiting for a validation from the Walloon DSO""; High
PV Data Collection, "Collection of the Data PV to add it in Karno's optimisation model	Not Started		2025-10	2025-11	High

Booster control, "Hardware implementation to control and monitoring of booster (domestic hot water production on apartment)	Not Started		2025-10		Need to fix a date"; Medium
Awareness?, "Sensibilisation event to discuss about the network and defend our business case with the clients/users	In Progress		2025-10		Business Model Acceptance of the consumers and understanding of the technology"; Medium
Test Period, "Observation period once everything is operational (Forecast + Optimization + User communication)	Not Started		2026-03	2026-06	
Final Version Observation Period, "Observation period of the Final Version	Not Started		2027-01	2027-06	

VI.2. Pilot #2 AMB

#2 AMB

Title	Task Description	Status September 2025	Support WPs	Type of support needed	Start Date	End Date
MB + CCB + IEB - IT infrastructure	To collect data, store, and be able to define all the pipelines is needed to set up the basic IT framework (DDBB creation pipeline engine...)	Completed	WP6	Definition of the framework structure (D6.1)	2025-08-01	2025-08-31
MB - Optimisation	In parallel to the modelling, there is a need to define the optimisation algorithm and strategy.	In Progress	WP3	In coordination with the DT model, the optimisation needs to be defined in which the model will be used.	2025-09-09	2025-12-31

MB + CCB + IEB - Market interaction	In all buildings, the implicit and explicit flexibility utilisation will be tested. For this, it is necessary to define the connection to them and how the interaction is set, which strategy is determined to operate in or between these markets. Hybrid operation between them?	Not Started	WP5	Expected an indication or definition of the interaction or strategy to interact with the different markets for implicit or explicit operation. This task is expected to be linked to the WP3 optimisation.	2025-10-01	2025-12-31
CCB - Optimisation	In parallel to the modelling, in the CCB, there is a need to define the optimisation algorithm and strategy.	Not Started	WP3	In coordination with the DT model, the optimisation in which the model will be used needs to be defined.	2026-02-01	2026-03-31
IEB - Hardware quotation	Receive, review, and approve the provider's quotation for the hardware (BMS to replace the old one; use electricity from PV to heat the pool with 12kW heater) installation in the sports centre.	In Progress			2025-07-01	2025-10-31
IEB - User Interaction tool definition	Define a user interaction tool to inform users when it is optimal to charge their EV based on local renewable energy generation (needed for final quotation requirements definition). Lighting based.	In Progress	WP4	Define strategy to interact with users within the EV Charging recommendations for later define the hardware requirements.	2025-07-01	2025-09-30
IEB - Data collection	Collect data to accumulate enough historical information to begin training some models. All hardware installation needs to be completed first; this will be addressed later. In this step, the connection to the centralised IT architecture will be set	Not Started	WP6	Define a strategy for interacting with users within the EV Charging recommendations to define the hardware requirements later.	2026-03-01	2026-05-31

	and the data will be mapped and harmonised to the data model.					
IEB - Digital Twin	Create a DT from the different assets from the IEB.	Not Started			2026-06-01	2026-08-31
IEB - Algorithms deployment +test	Test of the DT - optimisation on the building.	Not Started			2026-09-01	2026-10-31
MB+CCB+IEB - Social evaluation	Evaluate the behavioural changes in users' interactions with EV chargers and their impact on energy consumption. This evaluation will include reformulations and reevaluations to ensure that project expectations are met.	Not Started	WP4	It is expected the evaluation of user actuation, and if needed, adjustments or changes to improve user engagement.	2026-11-01	2028-06-30
Final report and conclusions	Evaluation and report of the pilot achievements in the project.	Not Started	WP2+WP6	Support in providing the data and providing the target definitions (KPIs) (support on what is defined from task #18).	2027-07-01	2027-10-31

VI.3. Pilot #3 WeSmart

#3 WeSmart

Title	Task Description	Status September 2025	Support WPs	Type of support needed	Start Date	End Date	Challenges
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<p>Participants & Equipment</p>	<p>Select Participants and Equipment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·Identify and recruit pilot participants based on energy consumption profiles ·Select and prepare monitoring equipment for real-time energy measurement ·Define participant groups for control and test scenarios 	<p>Completed</p>	<p>WP4</p>	<p>IT Support</p> <p>Mobilisation of stakeholders in Greenbizz</p>	<p>2025-09-01</p>		<p>Initial participant selection complexity due to diverse energy profiles and residential users not very available</p> <p>What we learned:</p> <p>People with low energy consumption didn't feel they had much to contribute</p> <p>Privacy concerns around sharing consumption data were stronger than anticipated</p> <p>New strategy with Luc from Greenbizz:</p> <p>After talking with users from Greenbizz (who joined the workshop), we've come up with a broader approach that should work better:</p> <p>Expanding our ambassador pool beyond just residential users.</p> <p>Targeting both residential participants from energy communities and Greenbizz workspace.</p>
<p>Deploy Dongles/Greenbizz</p>	<p>Deploy dongles at Greenbiz pilot site for real-time energy data collection; maybe check on the MQTT solution (EWH?)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·Install energy monitoring dongles at strategic points in the Greenbizz facility ·Configure network connectivity for real-time data transmission ·Evaluate MQTT protocol implementation for reliable data exchange 	<p>In Progress</p>	<p>check if others have experience with Dongles WP6</p>	<p>Feedback needed from Sibelga</p>	<p>2025-09-01</p>	<p>2025-12-31</p>	<p>Coordination with Sibelga for installation scheduling (Person back from holidays end of Sep). API integration complexity with multiple energy providers; Real-time data processing scalability; GDPR compliance for energy consumption data</p>

Data collection : setup	Set up data collection backend and real-time monitoring infrastructure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·Design database architecture for energy consumption metrics ·Implement secure API endpoints for data ingestion ·Configure real-time monitoring dashboards for operational oversight 	In Progress	WP6	IT Support Data Mapping Prepare software to collect measurements, store and make it reachable for other Bluebird components	2025-10-01	2026-01-31	Data collection challenge is in the mapping of data, setting proper definitions and API connection between existing WeSmart solutions and third parties. A clear API definition and management approach should be defined to properly make the system work between different IT applications and also ensure data transfers and streaming securely. GDPR constraints should be taken into consideration: anonymization of personal data, data storage rules, DPO
Testing	'- Technical tests and calibration of dongles and data transmission from the Dongles to the WeSmart platform - Testing of algorithm computation - Testing of results of recommendations and feedback from users ·Validate data accuracy and transmission reliability between dongles and platform·Test optimization algorithms under various load scenarios ·Evaluate user interface for recommendation delivery and feedback collection'	Planned	WP6	IT Support	2025-11-01	2026-02-28	
Data Collection: ongoing	Ongoing data collection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·Monitor continuous data flow from all connected endpoints ·Implement data quality checks and missing data handling procedures ·Document baseline 	Not Started	WP3	IT Support	2026-01-01	2026-12-31	

	consumption patterns for later comparison						
Data Computation	Data Computation via BlueBird algorithms a) build models b) set up alg c) analyse results d) implement recommendations ·Develop prediction models for peak consumption periods ·Design optimization algorithms targeting peak reduction ·Create personalized recommendation engine based on consumption patterns	Not Started	WP3	IT Support	2026-04-01	2027-07-01	
Impact Analysis	Impact report and recommendations ·Measure peak reduction achieved through behavioral changes ·Evaluate user engagement with recommendations ·Quantify energy flexibility potential across different user profiles	Not Started	WP3	IT Support	2026-10-01	2027-12-31	

VI.4. Pilot #4 ENEA-Office

#4 ENEA-Office

Title	Task Description	Status September 2025	Support WPs	Type of support needed	Start Date	End Date
Inventory of currently existing equipment	Familiarization with the full documentation and equipment of the building (Access Points, technical rooms)	Completed			2025-01	2025-02

Local visits with PSNC	Familiarization with currently existing devices, development of a concept of operation	Completed			2025-01	2025-02
Network security requirements	Consultations with units responsible for network security in the Enea Capital Group	Completed			2025-03	2025-05
Creating documentation for the tender procedure	Development of a contract template with lawyers, development of a description of the subject of the contract, consultations with the substantive units of Enea Operator	Completed			2025-03	2025-05
Conducting market research for tenders	Conducting a market analysis of the tender procedure in accordance with the provisions of public procurement law, receiving offers from 5 potential contractors	Completed			2025-06	2025-07
Building a BMS server	Fulfilling the requirements for the BMS server, building a network resource for the BMS server by the outsourcing company of the Enea Capital Group - Enea Centrum	Completed			2025-06	2025-08
Software configuration for the BMS server	Software configuration for the BMS server in cooperation with PSNC and external sensor provider	In Progress	WP5	Prepare software to collect measurements, store and make it reachable for other Bluebird components	2025-08	2026-03
Tender procedure	Tender procedure	Not Started				2025-10
Signing a contract with the contractor	Signing a contract with the contractor	Not Started				2025-1

Installation and configuration of hardware with the BMS server	Installation and configuration of hardware with the BMS server	Not Started			2025-09	2026-02
Achieving full readiness for online data collection for the BlueBird project	Achieving full readiness for online data collection for the BlueBird project	Not Started		Final tests and configurations		2026-02
Local BMS server configuration and tests	Home assistant configuration (many instances) test with newly installed hardware	Not Started	WP5	IT support		2026-03
Interaction Tool for building mangers	UI to present measurements, adjust set points; one instance for manager, but differentiated into several sections of the building	Not Started	WP5	IT support		2026-12
Use case: Predictive heating and monitoring	Case study tests: Predictive heating and monitoring	Not Started	WP2, WP3			
Use case: Heating control with the use of remote thermostats	Case study tests: Heating control with the use of remote thermostats	Not Started	WP2			
Use case: Flexibility in heat consumption	Case study tests: Flexibility in heat consumption – a recommendation system to support user's decisions concerning thermostat settings in a predictive way to respect comfort constraints	Not Started	WP2, WP5, WP4?			
Data Analysis	Energy consumption (BlueBird Digital Twins) and price forecasts, local consumption optimization, flexibility	Not Started	WP3?	IT support		2026-12

	management to reduce the energy cost					
Additional functions, reports, evaluation	Bluebird and energy markets Integration tests, preparing final reports and conclusions	Not Started		IT support		2027-12

VI.5. Pilot # 5 ENEA- Grid

#5 ENEA-Grid

Title	Task Description	Status September 2025	Support WPs	Type of support needed	Start Date	End Date
Inventory of currently existing equipment	Familiarization with the full documentation and equipment of the building (Access Points, technical rooms)	Completed			2025-01	2025-02
Local visits with PSNC	Familiarization with currently existing devices, development of a concept of operation	Completed			2025-01	2025-02
Network security requirements	Consultations with units responsible for network security in the Enea Capital Group	Completed			2025-03	2025-05
Creating documentation for the tender procedure	Development of a contract template with lawyers, development of a description of the subject of the contract, consultations with the substantive units of Enea Operator	Completed			2025-03	2025-05
Conducting market research	Conducting a market analysis of the tender procedure in accordance with the provisions of public procurement law, receiving offers from 5 potential contractors	Completed			2025-06	2025-06

Building a BMS server	Fulfilling the requirements for the BMS server, building a network resource for the BMS server by the outsourcing company of the Enea Capital Group - Enea Centrum	Completed			2025-06	2025-08
Software configuration for the BMS server	Software configuration for the BMS server in cooperation with PSNC and external sensor provider	In Progress	WP5	Prepare software to collect measurements, store and make it reachable for other Bluebird components	2025-08	2026-03
Tender procedure	Tender procedure	Not Started				2025-10
Signing a contract with the contractor	Signing a contract with the contractor	Not Started				2025-10
Installation and configuration of hardware with the BMS server	Installation and configuration of hardware with the BMS server	Not Started				2026-02
Achieving full readiness for online data collection for the BlueBird project	Achieving full readiness for online data collection for the BlueBird project	Not Started				2026-02
Local BMS server configuration and tests	Home assistant configuration and test with newly installed hardware	Not Started	WP5	IT support		2026-03
Energy market Integration	Integration with Polish day ahead market and capacity market with Trading Manager	In Progress	WP 5	IT support	2025-08	2026-01
User Interaction Tool	UI to present measurements (ready to present more than one	Not Started	WP5	IT support		2026-12

	ENEA Grid building), adjust set points					
Data Analysis	Energy consumption and price forecasts (Bluebird Digital Twins), local consumption optimization, flexibility management to reduce the energy cost, integration with Knowledge Engine	Not Started	WP3?	IT support		2026-12
Use case: Simple non-intrusive building electric heating and cooling - monitoring and prediction	Case study tests: Simple non-intrusive building electric heating and cooling - monitoring and prediction	Not Started	WP2			
Use case: Optimize to generate actuations o heating: generate target temperatures for thermostats o cooling: generate on/off patterns for ACs	Case study tests: Optimize to generate actuations o heating: generate target temperatures for thermostats o cooling: generate on/off patterns for ACs	Not Started	WP2			
Use case: Demonstrate the use of a dynamic heating & cooling management as a preparation for TSO interaction	Case study tests: Demonstrate the use of dynamic heating & cooling management as preparation for TSO interaction.	Not Started	WP2			
Additional functions,	Bluebird and energy markets Integration tests (Utilization of Trading Manager,	Not Started	WP5	IT support		2027-12

reports, evaluation	testing one of the standard market protocols) preparing final reports and conclusions					
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VI.6. Pilot #6 Enlion

#6 Enlion

Title	Task Description	Status September 2025	Support WPs	Start Date	End Date
VPP: prepare new data connection	Prepare technical and operational requirements for the new data connection between the waterworks and the VPP	In Progress	WP6	2025-09	2025-11
VPP: implement data connection	Implement the established data connection and validate data flow to the VPP platform	In Progress	WP6	2025-09	2025-11
VPP: Data collection	Continuously collect real-time and historic data from the waterworks to feed the VPP and enable flexibility trading	Not Started	Wp6	2025-12	2026-12
Prepare Data Structures	Define and implement data structures for exchange between waterworks, VPP, and Bluebird system	In Progress	WP6	2025-11	2025-12
Prepare interfaces	Prepare system interfaces (APIs, protocols, security) to ensure stable communication between systems	In Progress	WP6	2025-11	2025-1
Testing of interfaces	Conduct unit tests, integration tests, and load tests for the interfaces, incl. documentation of results	Not Started	WP6	2025-12	2026-03
Integration with BlueBird System	Implement and test integration with the Bluebird automation system	Not Started	WP6	2025-11	2026-03
Implement BlueBird services	Implementation of the services required by the Bluebird system	Not Started	WP6	2026-02	2026-0

	(e.g., data processing, control commands, monitoring)				
Testing and Evaluation of BlueBird services	Functional and operational testing of Bluebird services, incl. performance evaluation and documentation of improvements	Not Started	WP6,WP7	2026-03	2026-04
Clarify and settle data sources	Clarify all required data sources (sensors, controllers, databases); define access, quality assurance, and update cycles	In Progress	WP3,WP6	2025-10	2025-11
Waterworks flexibility integration	Upgrade the waterworks building to provide positive and negative flexibility to the VPP, including water tank storage utilization for energy flexibility and revenue generation. HW is already selected and will be ordered. Offer for service of integration is open. Establish new data service system (data pipeline)	In Progress		2025-09	2025-12
Forecasting: historic&live	Compile historic energy consumption data and set up live data sources to enable accurate short- and medium-term forecasting	In Progress	Wp3	2025-09	2026-03
Retention tank: optimization	Optimize usage of water tanks to increase energy flexibility and maximize efficiency of the waterworks operations	In Progress	WP3	2025-09	2025-11
Flex evaluation: Optimize	Implement optimization strategies to exploit flexibility potentials for operational efficiency and revenue maximization	Not Started	Wp5 WP3	2025-11	2026-03
Marketing: interface implementation	Implement an interface for market participation, enabling the waterworks to offer flexibility services	Not Started	Wp5	2026-02	2026-05
Test flexibility calls	Perform test calls with the market and VPP interfaces to validate technical communication (API, data exchange, response times) and responsiveness of flexibility offers (activation requests, confirmations, settlement signals)	Not Started	Wp5	2026-03	2026-12

Business model analysis	Analyse suitable business models for integrating the waterworks into energy markets incl. cost-benefit analysis	Not Started	WP4, WP5, WP7	2026-06	2027-01
Off-selling in energy communities	Develop and pilot flexibility offers for local energy communities	Not Started	WP5	2027-01	2027-08
Evaluation Procedure Alignment	Align with partners on a common evaluation methodology based on KPIs and monitoring setup to ensure comparability across demo sites	Not Started	WP7	2026-06	2027-01
KPI Definition and monitoring	Define quantitative and qualitative KPIs for energy flexibility, grid integration, and social impact; set up monitoring infrastructure	In Progress	WP7	2025-09	2026-03
Regulatory Framework mapping	Identify relevant national and EU regulations affecting flexibility provision of the waterworks; define compliance requirements	In Progress	WP4	2025-09	2026-01
User Interface tool	Develop and test a user interface tool for operators of the waterworks, including visualization of flexibility status, market participation and KPIs	Not Started	WP4	2025-11	2026-03
Markt strategy alignment	Align waterworks flexibility integration with identified market opportunities and regulatory boundaries	Not Started	WP4	2026-01	2026-04
Flex evaluation: Evaluate	Evaluate flexibility potentials of the waterworks building including peak shaving, demand response, and energy trading options	In Progress		2026-07	2026-12
Test, reports, evaluation	Bluebird and energy markets Integration Tests, preparing final reports and evaluation of scalability, replicability and business feasibility	Not Started		2026-12	2027-12

VI.7. Pilot#7 EWH

Abbreviations (many UCs):

- PLB – Hotel Prinz-Luitpold-Bad
- Jubi – Hostel "Jugendbildungsstätte"
- CS – Cold Storage UC
- SC – Smart Charging UC

#7 EWH

Title	Task Description	Status September 2024	Support WPs	Start Date	End Date
PLB/Jubi: Analyse Building Infrastructure	Analysis of infrastructure and hardware in the pilot buildings	In Progress		2025-03	2025-09
PLB/Jubi: Analyse Business Case Potentials	Assessment of the flexibility potential of the properties	In Progress		2025-0	2025-11
CS_PLB: Setup Lorawan Network	Setup Lorawan Network in PLB to get data from the surrounding, power data, door status etc (with IoT team) reason: CS in the basement	In Progress		2025-09	2025-09
CS_Jubi: Lorawan setup	If Luitpold planning is successful and sensor selection is complete repeat Lorwan setup steps for Luitpold Bad			2025-09	2025-12
CS_PLB: Lorwan Sensor Selection	After Meeting in PLB on 26. choose Sensors for Temperature and Power measurements	In Progress		2025-09	2025-10
CS_PLB: Install Lorawan Sensors	Installation in PLB	Not Started		2025-10	2025-11
CS_PLB: Start measuring	where is data gathered if no bluebird database is ready ==> collect data locally first, then figure out how to communicate data. Then data is available for modeling!			2025-11	2025-11
CS_PLB: API or MQTT Sensor Readout	Define interconnections with Enlion and integrate our sensors into Bluebird IT infrastructure,		WP6 and Enlion	2025-12	2025-12
CS_PLB/Jubi Launch cold storage supportive structure	Setup the IT system with enlion? -when can we integrate WP3 Modelling and Control? -		WP6, Enlion, WP3	2025-1	2026-01
CS_PLB/Jubi: New Control Units	Select and Buy Setup New Refrigeration Control Units, current control unit	In Progress		2025-09	2025-12

	doesn't support smartness; check price label				
CS_PLB_Jubi: EWH Control Unit	To Implement the Bluebird optimization, the optimization has to be translated from the server to a protocol readable by the refrigeration control units. For this an extra control unit has to be selected, bought, programmed and implemented. This will also transmit data from inside the cold storage rooms to the database. CHALLENGE: FIND HARDWARE			2025-09	2026-03
CS: Provide Data for Modeling	provide data for modeling from cold storage rooms		WP3	2025-12	2025-12
CS_PLB/Jubi Start pilot operation	Try to operate whole system with Optimization from WP3 - develop testing and "implementation plan" for secure launch on site		WP3	2026-03	2026-03
SC: Testdata	historic data is available; but release form needs to signed and send to WPs (for both PLB/Jubi)		WP3	2025-10	2025-10
SC_PLB: determine technology Partner	there are multiple options for a technical partner for controlling the charging stations. For the Project we have to select one (The inncharge case!)			2025-09	2025-10
SC_PLB: define interconnections with technology partner	Define interconnections between technology partner and bluebird infrastructure for User input data and charging data transfer		Enlion,		
SC_PLB: setup technology partner control of charging station	change sim cards, reprogram urls etc			2026-01	2026-01
SC_PLB: develop GUI	Inetum has to develop GUI to get user input for smart charging, Seeburg is needed for input on the information that has to be displayed		WP4 inetum seeburg	2025-1	2026-01
Setup Bluebird supportive it infrastructure	setup bluebird infrastructure on enlion servers to have a database		Enlion	2025-11	2026-01

SC_PLB: Bluebird infrastructure integration	combine bluebird infrastructure and technology partners infrastructure and start operation			2026-02	2026-03
SC_PLB: Start pilot operation	Try to operate whole system with GUI and gather Data for WP4 - develop testing and "implementation plan" for secure launch on site - when do we add wp3 optimization		Enlion,	2026-04	2026-04
SC_Jubi:	Discuss use case with Jubi			2025-10	2025-10
Define further goals	Evaluate Progress and Use cases, evaluate possibility of further use cases or increased complexity of use cases,			2026-03	2026-03
SRI/ KPI review 2026				2026-07	2026-07
SRI/KPI review 2027				2027-06	2027-06
Evaluate Energy community for PLB	As the Hotel with its PV and CHP is on a different connection then the charging stations, it could be interesting to evaluate options to enable energy sharing between the connections (over the grid)			2026-05	2026-06
Testing, Optimisation	If necessary, adjust the GUI for optimization or test different variants.			2026-05	2027-01
Analyse & Evaluate Data	Ongoing support for the pilot project and analysis of systems and data			2026-08	2027-07
Concept Scalling up	Development of a concept for potential transferability of the pilot project based on initial findings			2027-01	2027-04
Final report and conclusions	preparing final reports and evaluation of scalability, replicability and business feasibility			2027-06	2027-11